

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D3.4 Biodiversity observation network data online available in the DTO repositories_M20

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
ARMS	Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures
BODC	British Oceanographic Data Centre
CGFS	Channel Ground Fish Survey
CPICS	Continuous Plankton Imaging and Classification System
CTD	Conductivity Temperature Depth

DEFRA	Department for Environment Food & Rural Affairs
DUC	Demonstrator Use Case
DwC-A	Darwin Core Archive
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EDITO-Infra	EU Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin Ocean
EMO BON	European Marine Omics Biodiversity Observation Network
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
ETN	European Tracking Network
EU DTO	European Union Digital Twin of the Ocean
EurOBIS	European Ocean Biodiversity Information System
EEA	European Environment Agency
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GES	Good Environmental Status
GPS	Global Positioning System
HELCOM	Helsinki Commission
IFCB	Imaging Flow Cyto Bot
IMIS	Integrated Marine Information System
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
IPT	Integrated Publishing Toolkit
LTETS	Long Term Time Series
MRU	Marine Reporting Unit
MEOW	Marine Ecoregions Of the World
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NBN	National Biodiversity Trust
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NIS	Non-Indigenous Species
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System

OSPAR	Oslo and Paris Conventions
PAM	Passive acoustic monitoring
ROIs	Regions of Interest
ROV	Remotely operated vehicles
SEANOE	Sea Open Scientific Data Publication
UVP	Underwater Vision Profiler
WISE	Water Information System for Europe
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species

Keywords

Data Products; Genomics; Imaging; Biologging; Passive Acoustic Monitoring; Citizen science; Literature

Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To understand the current state of marine systems and their pressures, as well as to advance knowledge, it is essential to have comprehensive and accessible marine biodiversity data. Protecting and restoring biodiversity is one of three objectives of the Horizon Europe Mission to restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030, enabling the EU to reach its Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 targets. Within this context, the EU aims to build a digital environment, the EU Digital Twin Ocean (DTO), that allows to create a digital replica of ocean processes to improve their understanding, their response to changes in the system, and to simulate alternative scenarios, which will ultimately allow for better informed decision-making.

Despite previous efforts from the EU, large amounts of biodiversity data still do not find their way into repositories due to several reasons, including cultural, legal, governance issues, lack of resources, or technical barriers. In the case of technical barriers, one of the problems may arise from systems not being able to integrate the type of biodiversity data being collected or the type of biodiversity data products being produced. Various instruments and new techniques can produce vast amounts of data and help to optimise the resources to collect and analyse biodiversity time series data. Nonetheless, the flow of these data into data repositories or integrators is still at distinct stages of development.

D3.3 ("DTO-BioFlow data product inventory") was the intermediate link between D3.1 ("DTO-BioFlow data flow Blueprint"), and D3.4 and D3.5 ("Biodiversity observation network data online available in the DTO repositories" in months 20 and 38 of the project). D3.3 provided a description of the datasets and/or data products that will be available and accessible through the EU DTO repositories (D3.4 and D3.5) through the envisioned data flows in D3.1.

The present deliverable, i.e. D3.4 details the first batch of data (described in the D3.3 inventory) to be available for use in the EU DTO via publication in EMODnet Biology (as described in D3.1). D3.4 builds on the work of D3.3 and it is produced as an update to the inventory. A second update will be provided in D3.5, due in month 38 (i.e. October 2026), which aims to detail the information of the second batch of data made available, thus ensuring that the information in D3.3 is up to date by the end of the project.

D3.3 presented a summary of available, yet inaccessible in certain cases, marine biodiversity data, including metadata descriptions, which will be made accessible through data products created within WP3 (*Enabling sustained flows of biodiversity monitoring data into the DTO*). The report described the datasets selected (and the data products created) for each of the biodiversity data types relevant in the different tasks of WP3 (e.g., genomics observation networks; plankton imaging observation networks; fish, mammal and bird biologging networks; cetacean passive acoustic observation networks; and other relevant biodiversity data sources).

In D3.4 the number of datasets published via EMODnet for each data type are mentioned, and links to the published data records in EMODnet are provided in a table in the Appendix. In addition, significant updates regarding the standardisation work and the data flow status are briefly summarised for each data type in yellow boxes on each section. During the first 20 months of the project significant effort has been made for each data type to transform the datasets to adhere to the relevant standards, and to develop the data flows needed. Originally, 231 datasets were included in the inventory in D3.3. During the update for D3.4, 16 additional datasets have been identified to be made available for the EU DTO. To date, a total of 29 datasets have been published in EMODnet (25 newly published, and four updated with the latest data), setting the basis for the future work.

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1. Introduction

D3.4 ("Biodiversity observation network data online available in the DTO repositories") provides an update of the datasets/data products from the data product inventory (D3.3) that have been made available during the first 20 months of the project according to the data flows described in the Blueprint (D3.1). D3.4 and the future D3.5 aim to keep the data product inventory from D3.3 relevant and up to date by the project end.

During the first 20 months of project significant work has taken place to ensure that the datasets adhere to the relevant standards, and to develop the data flows needed for each data type. Since D3.4 is an update of D3.3, the text across the following sections has been maintained. The updates in this deliverable are contained within yellow boxes for each section where updates are relevant, such as the present one. The updates provided in D3.4 mention the number of datasets published via EMODnet for each data type, along with relevant updates regarding the data flow status, and relevant work that can complement and update the information provided in D3.3. The inventory list has been updated with 16 additional datasets that were identified after the submission of D3.3, bringing the updated data product inventory to 247 datasets/data products. The updated list can be found in the table in the Appendix, which now also includes the links to the published data records in EMODnet.

Throughout the updates below, work sometimes refers to the "EU DTO" and sometimes to the "EDITO data lake". As explained in the introduction below, the EDITO-Infra project is developing the EU DTO infrastructure. The mentions to the "EDITO data lake" in the updates below refer to the short-term implementations needed to deliver the data to this infrastructure, while the "EU DTO" refers to the larger scale concept, not limited only to the infrastructure.

To understand the current state of marine systems and their pressures, as well as to advance knowledge, it is essential to have comprehensive and accessible marine biodiversity data. Protecting and restoring biodiversity is one of three objectives of the Horizon Europe Mission to Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030, enabling the EU to reach its Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 targets. Within this context, the EU aims to build a digital environment, the EU Digital Twin Ocean (EU DTO), that allows to create a digital replica of ocean processes to improve our understanding, predict their response to changes in the system, and to simulate alternative scenarios, which will ultimately lead to making better informed decisions.

Despite previous efforts from the EU, large amounts of biodiversity data do not find their way into repositories due to a variety of reasons, for example of a technical barrier, when existing platforms, databases and repositories are not able to accommodate for the biodiversity data being produced, due to the way they were originally designed. Various instruments and new observing techniques such as DNA-based observations, plankton imaging observations, passive acoustics, or biologging data, can produce vast amounts of data and help to optimize the resources to collect and analyze biodiversity time series data. Nonetheless, the flow of these data into data repositories or integrators is at distinct stages of development and for some, the guidance is still a work in progress, subject to frequent changes as more information becomes available.

The project DTO-BioFlow aims to increase the flow of relevant biodiversity data into the EU DTO. Work Package (WP) 3 'Enabling sustained flows of biodiversity monitoring data into the DTO', aims to set up the general data flow towards the EU DTO, establishing the connection towards this EU infrastructure and ensuring that sustainable data flows are in place beyond the lifetime of the project. This WP will focus on biodiversity data types from different sources: (1) genomics observation networks, (2) plankton imaging observation networks, (3) fish, mammal and bird biologging networks, (4) cetacean passive acoustic observation networks, and (5) other relevant biodiversity data sources. These biodiversity data types, some of which are quite new to the scientific community, along with other relevant biodiversity data sources will contribute data for the demonstration of an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring with policy relevant use cases in WP4 'Demonstrate with policy-relevant use cases'. Ultimately, these data will flow towards

the EU DTO infrastructure developed under initiatives such as the EDITO-Infra project, with WP5 ‘Integration in DTO infrastructure’ supporting this integration of marine biodiversity data into the EU DTO infrastructure. This interconnection among WPs is planned to build a coherent structure of data sources and use case applications.

The current document aims to present an online inventory with metadata description of data products created within WP3, i.e., it is a document describing the datasets selected (and data products created) by WP3 for each of the biodiversity data types that WP3 focuses on (e.g., genomics observation networks; plankton imaging observation networks; fish, mammal and bird biologging networks; cetacean passive acoustic observation networks; and other relevant biodiversity data sources). This document is the second consecutive deliverable of WP3, following “D3.1 DTO-BioFlow data flow blueprint” which described the envisioned data flows (Figure 1) and set up the general framework for data flow towards the DTO for each of the aforementioned biodiversity data types.

The diagram shown in Figure 1 is a simplified version of the data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow. All activities start with the data collection, which can be done via in situ or remote sensors and/or human observation. Data collected by DTO-BioFlow partners will be subjected to several processing steps (not covered in this diagram). Depending on the type of data, data may be first submitted to an integrator or repository, or directly go into EMODnet Biology. Data in repositories might also be shared with integrators before being made available in EMODnet Biology. In EMODnet Biology, various procedures are implemented to ensure the data are quality checked to avoid publishing data with issues. If issues are encountered, the originators are informed so these can be addressed ahead of publication, thus ensuring that all data are of high quality. All data available via EMODnet Biology will be harvested by the EU DTO and will be findable in the EU DTO Data Lake. This will require a few processing steps, more specifically a reformatting to cloud optimised formats which will allow for faster and more efficient queries.

Figure 1 - Envisaged general data flow diagram towards EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO.

This data product inventory in D3.3 is the intermediate link between D3.1 (the data flow Blueprint) and D3.4 (the biodiversity observation network data online available in the DTO repositories), as it provides a description of the datasets and/or data products that will be available and accessible through the DTO repositories (D3.4) through the envisioned data flows (D3.1). Each chapter of this document will be listing the available datasets and/or data products for the specific data types that will be included in the EDITO-Infra Data Lake. In addition, in case said datasets and data products are not yet available, the specific issues hindering the data transformation and data flow will be listed in detail.

In order to harmonise the DTO-BioFlow outputs, in terms of data and data products, it was decided to adhere to the “Processing Levels” established by EMODnet that can be found in the Data and Data Product Portfolio available through

the EMODnet website via the following [link](#). These levels are in place for EMODnet and work is ongoing to include these levels in the BODC NVS2, which will allow for an adequate governance structure to the definitions presented in Table 4. For the purposes of the Blueprint document and to achieve a better harmonisation with EMODnet practices, the anticipated DTO-BioFlow data and data product outputs will be mapped against those levels. A data product is defined as an output resulting from the analysis or modelling of the in-situ data and that can include various interpolation techniques and parameters derived from the original data.

2. Data products from “Genomics” (Task 3.1)

As was also mentioned in the data flow Blueprint, “Genomic data” is an umbrella term but in the scope of the DTO-BioFlow project, we will mainly focus on taxonomically annotated nucleotide sequence data derived from bulk or environmental DNA (eDNA) samples subjected to either metabarcoding or metagenomic sequencing or both. Hence, we will be using the term “genomics” hereafter to refer to these types of approaches. eDNA refers to DNA that can be extracted from environmental samples such as soil, water or air (without any taxon targeted isolation first) (Taberlet et al., 2012) and it can derive from a variety of sources, such as shedding from organisms, cell lysis or biologically active propagules (Rodriguez-Ezpeleta et al., 2021).

The diagram included in Figure 2 is a schematic depiction of the genomics data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow. All activities will start with the data obtained from material samples which in most cases are collected by humans, although there can be cases where collection can be assisted and/or implemented by automated sampling devices. Automated devices are often also used after sample collection, e.g. for the PCR amplification and library preparation to minimise error rates and the hands-on time for the molecular analyses. Genomics data created and/or collected by DTO-BioFlow partners and associated projects can be submitted to data repositories or integrators; in the last case, data will undergo quality control steps dependent on the chosen integrator. Data in repositories might also be shared with integrators, after going through quality control steps, or they can become directly available in EMODnet Biology. Data from integrators can be either harvested from EMODnet Biology, or directly by the EU DTO in case they are data that do not fit EMODnet Biology’s data infrastructure. All data made available via EMODnet Biology will eventually be made available to the EU DTO and will be Findable, Accessible and Reusable in the DTO Data Lake.

Figure 2 - Schematic diagram showing the anticipated genomics data flows that will be captured within DTO-Bio Flow.

Task 3.1 aims to realize the genomics data flow towards the EU DTO. In order for this to be achieved, the task’s work is divided into different subtasks. In the first subtask (T3.1.1), genomics datasets in DTO-BioFlow will be created by test casing cost-effective biomonitoring solutions on eDNA collected from water filters (micro- and nanoplankton) and from hard substrate samples (i.e., from Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures, ARMS). ARMS have been shown to be highly

effective in detecting and monitoring marine non-indigenous species (NIS), especially newly introduced NIS (Pagnier et al., 2024). Often, water sample processing involves filtering through different pore size membranes, which is characterized as size-fractionation (Pascoal et al., 2023). This approach, apart from facilitating the filtering process, is also meaningful as it separates the sample into sub-communities, e.g. particle-attached and free-living, size classes, e.g. microplankton, picoplankton and nanoplankton, or even taxonomies, e.g., eukaryotes, prokaryotes and viruses (Atteia et al., 2023).

While there are several repositories for the submission of genomic datasets, and most of them have been already mentioned in the data-flow Blueprint (D3.1), we have focused on a specific data flow starting from the submission of the raw metabarcoding sequence files to EMBL-EBI's European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), or any other INSDC repository. These metabarcoding datasets, targeting the microbial biodiversity, are subsequently analysed by the MGnify resource of EMBL-EBI, either upon user-request or through the ongoing efforts of MGnify to periodically analyse nucleotide sequence data publicly available in ENA. MGnify uses standardised bioinformatic pipelines to produce these analyses, providing users (in the case of metabarcoding data) with a taxonomic annotation of the dataset based on different reference databases. The complement of reference databases utilised by the MGnify amplicon pipeline has been expanded to include the protist-focused PR2 database, which was added to the new version of this pipeline as part of this project, with a view to improving the eukaryotic representation (subtask T3.1.2). The taxonomically annotated occurrences generated by the MGnify analysis are then fetched by GBIF for aggregation in that resource. A similar flow of data products between MGnify and OBIS has not been operationalized yet, but is currently being explored in the framework of DTO-BioFlow, since effective data exchange and semantic interoperability will be revised to improve publication and discovery of genetic data in OBIS (subtask T3.1.2). In addition to the datasets that will be created in subtask T3.1.1, existing selected raw metabarcoding datasets are being analysed by MGnify and the outputs are being converted into DwC-A-ready data products for inclusion into the EU DTO and downstream analysis (subtask T3.1.3). An example subset of metabarcoding datasets targeting the 18S ribosomal gene will be prioritised for analysis with the new version of the pipeline to demonstrate the improvement afforded through addition of PR2 as a reference database. While final implementation of this new pipeline is underway in MGnify, including the generation of DwC-A-ready outputs, the pipeline has undergone validation and comparison against other analysis pipelines through participation in the Marco-Bolo project Data Analysis Challenge. Conversations about how and which MGnify data products will flow into the EU DTO are underway (T3.1.4). As MGnify data products are not limited to metabarcoding approaches, we are also investigating how some of the additional outputs produced by MGnify could be used in Demonstrator Use Cases (WP4). These efforts directly support the aim of sustainable ingestion procedures to connect the identified repositories and integrators to the EU DTO (subtask T3.1.4).

D3.4 Updates – Genomics data produced from EMO BON are being analysed to convert the outputs of the EMO BON data analysis (produced by the metaGOflow pipeline) to DwC files: first, only the taxonomic results will be used but at a later stage information on the functional potential will be also added in the DwC files, linked to each sample, using the eMoF (Extended Measurement or Fact) extension. This will be the first attempt to add shotgun metagenomics data into OBIS and EMODnet Biology.

The MGnify amplicon analysis pipeline is being updated to incorporate confidence estimates for taxonomic annotations, as well as additional sequence taxonomic identification using the PR2 reference database. In addition, several genomic (metabarcoding) datasets that were identified as important to include in the EU DTO have been analysed and are currently available on the MGnify platform; we are exploring ways of converting the analysed outputs into DwC format and directly submitting them either by creating a dedicated MGnify IPT instance, or by using the IPT instance of VLIZ.

Discussions are ongoing between OBIS, GBIF, and EMBRC-ERIC to identify ways to harmonise ingestion procedures. Some of the issues restricting the data flow from MGnify to OBIS (and subsequently to the EU DTO) are the inclusion of negative control (blank) samples in the datasets and the occurrence of prokaryotic species which do not have an AphiaID and cannot be matched to the WoRMS taxonomy. Prokaryotic taxonomic databases (such as the Genome

Taxonomy Database (GTDB) and the List of Prokaryotic names with Standing in Nomenclature (LPSN)), have been proposed to be incorporated into the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) backbone taxonomy, so that all species identified in the plankton and ARMS genomics datasets can have an AphiaID when converted into DwC files.

Three of the ARMS-genomics datasets identified in D3.3 have already been published by EMODnet Biology. The datasets were prepared by DTO-BioFlow partners (VLIZ, EMBRC-ERIC, UGOT), submitted to OBIS and they were later ingested by EurOBIS and EMODnet.

The majority of the datasets identified in D3.3 that are analysed by MGNify and harvested by GBIF, do not pass the EMODnet quality control checks. Several issues have been identified, among which the most common is the lack of AphiaIDs in the GBIF DwC files. We are currently in the process of communicating with the data providers (where applicable) and GBIF in an attempt to correct those issues. The detailed process for the correction of errors is being documented in a dedicated GitHub repository: <https://github.com/cpavloud/Genomics DTO-BioFlow>

2.1. ARMS Genomics Data products

The majority of the ARMS datasets that we have identified as priority under Task 3.1 and that are described in this document are deriving from the ARMS-MBON (Marine Biodiversity Observation Network) network. ARMS-MBON was established with the aim to assess the status and changes in marine hard-bottom benthic communities with genomic-based methods, notably DNA metabarcoding, in combination with image-based identifications (Obst et al., 2020). ARMS-MBON was primarily funded through the Joint Research Activity (JRA1) of ASSEMBLE Plus, with financial contributions from the Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management, the Interreg project GEANS and with considerable in-kind contributions by the participating institutes; currently, it continues under the European Marine Omics Biodiversity Observation Network (EMO BON) project (Santi et al., 2023), coordinated by the European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC).

The first ARMS-MBON dataset has been thoroughly described in a related publication (Daraghmeh et al., 2024); it includes data from the 2018 and 2019 ARMS deployments, which were retrieved in 2018, 2019 and 2020. The dataset contains 32,054 records derived from sequencing 197 samples from 56 ARMS units for 3 genes (18S rRNA, COI, ITS).

Additional ARMS datasets, i.e., datasets not deriving from the ARMS-MBON network, have also been identified, namely a dataset from the Red Sea (with ARMS retrieved in 2014), which has been analysed by MGNify, and another one from North Sea (with ARMS retrieved in 2022), which has been deposited in GBIF. The location of all the aforementioned ARMS genomics datasets is shown in Figure 3. It is evident that there are certain geographical gaps, e.g. across the Mediterranean where the ARMS datasets are rather scarce and the Black Sea. Details on the ARMS datasets are provided in the Appendix table.

Figure 3 – Map showing the location of the ARMS genomics datasets.

2.2. Plankton genomics data products

Task 3.1 has identified 85 plankton genomics datasets, across 7637 locations around the world, that should become accessible through the EU DTO, within the duration of the project. This is a compilation of datasets that are considered valuable for the EU DTO since they are derived from coordinated genomic observation networks, monitoring programs, long term time-series observatories (such as the Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory and the Western Channel Observatory), as well as from worldwide sampling campaigns (such as the Ocean Sampling Day (Kopf et al., 2015), Tara Oceans (Sunagawa et al., 2020) and the Malaspina 2010 Circumnavigation Expedition (Duarte, 2015)). These datasets are mostly available through MGnify, which was already identified in the data flow Blueprint document (D3.1) as a major data repository/integrator, and some of them have been also harvested by GBIF (for details, see the table in the Appendix).

In the following map (Figure 4), the locations of the selected plankton datasets are shown. Due to the inclusion of data from global sampling campaigns, the selected datasets that will become available in the EU DTO are not solely pertinent to European Seas. However, this is considered advantageous since it provides highly relevant information to the DUC 4.1 on invasive species.

Figure 4 – Map showing the location of the 85 selected plankton genomics datasets.

3. Data products from “Plankton Imaging” (Task 3.2)

Plankton imaging data is sourced from various observation networks and instruments, ranging from those that can provide taxonomically resolved images to those that supply only particle data, as well as instruments capable of recording both particle data and images. Taxonomically resolved plankton imagery data products in DTO-BioFlow are provided by cameras on Remotely Operated Vehicules (ROV), camera traps, FlowCam, ZooScan, Cytosense, and Imaging Flow Cyto Bot (IFCB), and are generally processed with delayed-mode quality control checks. Instruments supplying both imagery and particle data include the SilCam, the Continuous Particle Imaging and Classification System (CPICS), and the Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP; versions 5 and 6, v6 being deployed on Argo floats). This overall data flow is already functional for monitoring time series collected with specific instruments and is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – Schematic diagram showing the plankton imaging data flows that will be captured within DTO-Bio Flow.

Data products with taxonomic information are described in Section 3.1. Plankton taxonomy from imaging. Data products from instruments that primarily provide particle data are detailed in Section 3.2. Particle counts from imaging. A map showing the spatial coverage of plankton imaging data products is provided in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Map of the spatial coverage of plankton imaging data products focused on EU seas. In addition to those, the UVP particles data will be provided from worldwide datasets.

Tools

While fit-for-purpose tools have been or are being developed to analyse these datasets (described below in further detail), a few datasets will go to the intermediary repositories EcoTaxa and EcoPart before being sent to EMODnet Biology, and the EU DTO will benefit from improvements of these tools, currently under development.

EcoTaxa

EcoTaxa is an image classification web application, in which a large number of images can be uploaded together with metadata, classified with the assistance of AI models, and exported in various formats. It hosts data from many plankton imaging instruments (ZooScan, FlowCam, UVP, IFCB, and soon CytoSense, CPICS, etc.). Each instrument comes with different sampling protocols and metadata.

To yield ecologically meaningful data that goes beyond occurrences, a solution is being developed for users to compute concentrations and biovolumes from the metadata they import in EcoTaxa and the identifications they perform therein.

This will be achieved through the definition of formulas to compute three key quantities defined in the British Oceanographic Data Center NERC Vocabulary Server (BODC-NVS2):

- [sub-sampling coefficient](#) (no unit, in [0,1])
- [volume sampled of the water body](#) (in m³)
- [biovolume of biological entity specified elsewhere](#) (in mm³)

The graphical user interface may look like Figure 7.

Sampled volume of the water body in m3

This is the volume of water sampled within the sample or subsample, as appropriate for this dataset.

Sub-sampling coefficient in [0,1]

This is the fraction of the volume above that has been imaged.

Sample fields

Subsample fields

Figure 7 – Mockup of the graphical interface to be developed in EcoTaxa so that users can provide formulas to compute quantities that then allow EcoTaxa to compute concentrations and biovolumes.

Then EcoTaxa will be able to compute concentrations ([number of objects classified in a category / sub-sampling coefficient / volume sampled](#)) and biovolumes per unit water volume ([sum of individual biovolumes of objects classified in a category / sub-sampling coefficient / volume sampled](#)). These quantities will be exported in various formats, including inside DwC-A files that can be published in EMODnet Biology and subsequently available in the EU DTO.

EcoPart

EcoPart is a web application designed specifically to store and process UVP data, but which will also be able to handle particle and image data from the CPICS. EcoPart structures its information by size and will export depth-resolved particle size spectra to the EU DTO. However, in addition to being structured in size, marine particles can also be characterised morphologically. This can provide important information on their origin and sinking speed (Trudnowska et al., 2021). We are currently extending the approach presented in this paper to the worldwide datasets of UVP5 and 6 images and testing its robustness. This will then allow to classify, objectively and in a replicable way, any new set of images taken by these instruments, hence providing the international community with a common classification framework.

The prototype of this classification system should be ready by the end of the first quarter 2025. It will eventually be integrated in EcoPart (likely in 2026) for ease of use by the international community. At that point, the classification result, in addition to the size structure, may be provided to the EU DTO.

3.1. Plankton taxonomy from imaging

The following is an initial list of taxonomically resolved plankton imagery datasets that will become accessible through the EU DTO over the course of the project. The datasets are briefly described here, along with analysis tools that will be developed and made available on the EU DTO Data Lake and the EDITO-Infra; more details are available in the Appendix table.

3.1.1 LifeWatch observatory data: phytoplankton observations by FlowCam imaging in the Belgian Part of the North Sea

The LifeWatch observatory FlowCam dataset contains micro- and phytoplankton observations (occurrence and concentration data), primarily focusing on diatoms, dinoflagellates, and ciliates. The data are collected during monthly plankton sampling campaigns conducted in the Belgian part of the North Sea, starting in 2017 and continuing to the present. Nine coastal stations are sampled monthly, with additional offshore stations sampled seasonally to a total of 17 stations. Samples are taken using a 55 µm mesh size Apstein net and processed with a VS-4 FlowCAM model at 4x magnification, capturing images of objects ranging from 55–300 µm. The images are first classified taxonomically by an automated classifier and then validated by taxonomic experts. These data are submitted annually to EMODnet Biology (and subsequently will be available in the EU DTO); the dataset is continually updated to reflect the latest taxonomic revisions and data releases, as well as to incorporate accompanying environmental data alongside the biodiversity data.

D3.4 Updates – The LifeWatch micro- and phytoplankton FlowCam dataset was updated in January 2025 and published in EMODnet Biology in March 2025.

3.1.2 LifeWatch observatory data: zooplankton observations by imaging (ZooScan) in the Belgian Part of the North Sea

The LifeWatch observatory ZooScan dataset covers the same fixed marine stations as the LifeWatch FlowCam dataset and includes zooplankton observations (occurrence and concentration), starting in 2012 and continuing to the present. Samples are collected monthly using vertical WP2 net tows and imaged with the ZooScan, capturing size ranges from 300 µm to 5 cm. Taxonomic identifications are initially performed by an automated classifier and then manually validated by taxonomic experts. The data are published annually through EMODnet Biology and subsequently will be available to the DTO.

Tools

In addition to these two LifeWatch phytoplankton and zooplankton monitoring datasets, open access analysis tools will be available in the EDITO-Infra to carry out pelagic habitat assessments for pelagic habitat indicators 1, 2 and 3 (PH1, PH2 and PH3 respectively) using plankton imaging datasets. These tools include the Plankton Lifeform Extraction Tool (PLET) (Ostle et al., 2021), the PH1 PLET tool (Holland et al., 2023), the PelHabMSFD tool (Wacquet et al., 2024) and scripts to harvest Dwc-A plankton imaging datasets from the EU DTO data lake and aggregators like EMODnet Biology and to reformat these to the PLET and PelHabMSFD input requirements.

D3.4 Updates – The LifeWatch zooplankton ZooScan dataset was updated in January 2025 and published in EMODnet Biology in March 2025.

The accuracy of plankton and particle classification is being improved by refining training sets and improving taxonomic recognition. This included targeted improvements in the identification of specific taxa, such as *Bellerochea* sp. and *Branchiopoda*, as well as refining morphological classification criteria. Additionally, VLIZ assessed length measurements obtained from ZooScan, comparing them against microscopy-based measurements to ensure data reliability. Further efforts are being made to validate classification results, with over one million new annotations contributing to the ongoing refinement of models.

3.1.3 Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea

The Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO) dataset contains phytoplankton and zooplankton observations (occurrence and concentration) from continuous imagery monitoring in Helgoland (North Sea), from 2020 to present. Images of both particles and taxonomically resolvable objects are captured continuously by a Continuous Plankton Imaging and Classification System (CPICS) mounted on a Conductivity Temperature Depth (CTD) rosette deployed on a permanent mooring. Particle images from HUWO will be sent to the EcoPart repository (<http://ecopart.obs-vlfr.fr>) for further processing. Regions of Interest (ROIs) are automatically classified with a classifier developed by HEREON. Afterwards, taxonomically resolved ROIs are sent to EcoTaxa (<http://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr>), where a subset of these images is validated by taxonomic experts.

The pipeline to EcoPart and EcoTaxa is currently under development, and the dataset is expected to be available in EMODnet Biology and subsequently in the EU DTO by the end of the DTO-BioFlow project. The particle observations from the CPICS are further described in section

3.2.1 Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea.

D3.4 Updates – The HUWO taxonomically-resolved data is classified and exportable from EcoTaxa. Publication in EMODnet Biology is planned for either the April 2025 or June 2025 harvest. The particle data are waiting on the EcoPart NetCDF export functionality to send to the EDITO data lake, but the data is ready (no major changes to CPICS size spectra format).

The taxonomic classification algorithm for plankton and particles has been enhanced, classifying 15 million plankton images and 30 million particles from the CPICS.

3.1.4 SilCam taxonomic data from SINTEF Ocean / NTNU OceanLab Marine Observatory (OLMO)

The plankton imagery data that will be included in this dataset have been collected in Norwegian fjords (Norwegian Sea). A SINTEF Silhouette camera (SilCam) is deployed on profiling frames e.g., at the OceanLab Munkholmen Marine observatory surface buoy for opportunistic sampling. A few hundred thousand images were collected during several campaigns. A few thousand images are expected to be matched to a taxon, with the rest of the dataset being particles that are not taxon annotated. These images are automatically classified (and a set of probabilities to belong to each class is provided) and then spot-checked before being sent to the EU DTO. The dataset. A related dataset of particle size distribution, captured from the same images, is further discussed below.

Tools

SilCam images will be processed and classified using the PyOPIA pipeline (which includes a neural network). PyOPIA has been further developed for particles in the Iliad project to streamline the transmission of SilCam data to the EU DTO and other systems (<https://ocean-twin.eu/marketplace/product/pyopia>). Further metadata and standardisation work is ongoing in DTO-BioFlow.

D3.4 Updates – The SilCam images obtained during the September 2024 field campaign were not of high enough quality. Instead, images from past field work and projects are being used to improve the PyOPIA pipeline to the EDITO data lake and for exploitation in WP4, with further fieldwork anticipated to collect additional data.

Work is ongoing to improve PyOPIA to process SilCam instrument images. Partners are currently exploring how to establish a data flow from PyOPIA to the EDIT data lake directly or via **EcoTaxa/EcoPart** through a standardised netCDF format, similar to that established for the CPICS.

3.1.5 Macro-benthic species records from remote underwater videos along the Swedish West Coast

The Macro-benthic species records from remote underwater videos dataset consists of eight videos filmed by a baited remote underwater video camera in eight fjords along the Swedish west coast in September 2023. Species records were extracted from the movies using a Yolov8 model. This dataset contains fishes taxonomically identified at the species or family level, and crabs identified at the species level. This dataset is already published in GBIF and will be made available in the EU DTO, with an analysis available on Zenodo. While this dataset contains limited species observations, it is included in this document because much more data with similar format (i.e., fixed camera observatories) are expected to be added in the future.

D3.4 Updates – This dataset is currently undergoing a quality control evaluation prior to publication in EMODnet. It is planned to be published in either the April 2025 or June 2025 harvest.

3.1.6 Koster historical biodiversity assessment

The Koster historical biodiversity assessment dataset contains benthic observations from 70 videos recorded by remotely operated vehicles (ROVs) in the marine protected area of Kosterhavets National Park, off the Swedish west coast, filmed between 1997-2023. Species records of 17 species were extracted from the movies using a Yolov8 model. This dataset is already published in GBIF and will be made available in the EU DTO, with an analysis model available on Zenodo, similar to the one described in the previous section (see Appendix table).

Tools

Occurrences for the benthic datasets described in sections 3.1.5 and 3.1.6 were analysed following the SUBSIM software suite (<https://subsim.se/>), which includes functionality for data management, machine learning, digital collaboration, citizen science, and high-performance computing. Models produced by SUBSIM are published on Zenodo, with links to the respective data descriptions under “Analysis URL” in the Appendix data product inventory table.

D3.4 Updates – The Koster dataset was published in EMODnet Biology in February 2025.

The SUBSIM platform has been improved to standardise macroscopic image data from Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs) and Baited Remote Underwater Video trap systems (BRUVs).

3.1.7 IFCB Taxonomy data (CNRS LOG-ULCO)

The CNRS LOG-ULCO IFCB dataset contains phytoplankton data captured with an IFCB from weekly surveys of a Marine Protected Area (MPA) in the eastern English Channel, as well as from seasonal Channel Ground Fish Survey (CGFS) and International Bottom Trawl Survey (IBTS) cruises in the eastern English Channel and North Sea, from 2023 to present, and on dedicated plankton cruises in spring and summer 2024 (CARPARC and RioMAR Seine-MO). The MPA survey contains ~2M images, while the CGFS, IBTS and dedicated cruises contain ~10M images. The raw data will be pre-

processed with the Kraft et al. (2021), then uploaded to EcoTaxa for re-classification and validation. The dataset will then be made available to EMODnet Biology and subsequently to the EU DTO.

D3.4 Updates – Most of the IFCB data has been imported into EcoTaxa, but the classifications still need to be validated before export and publication in EMODnet Biology (currently planned for summer 2025).

3.1.8 CytoSense Taxonomy data (CNRS LOG-ULCO)

In addition to the aforementioned imaging flow cytometry datasets, presence/absence data from CytoSense imagery in the English Channel may also be provided. This will depend on the quality of the images and if technical limitations with the CytoSense are overcome. The spatial coverage would be the same as that of the IFCB dataset, but with greater temporal coverage. The images would be sent to EcoTaxa and classified using a classifier currently under development, before following the EcoTaxa-DTO pipeline.

D3.4 Updates – The CytoSense images have not yet been uploaded to EcoTaxa, but the CytoSense-EcoTaxa pipeline is ready for the import. Work is ongoing to develop a method to include summarised pulse shapes in EcoTaxa for export.

3.2. Particle counts from imaging

The following datasets contain size-resolved instead of taxonomy-resolved data on marine particles. Some are complementary datasets to the ones described above, issuing from the same instruments and observation campaigns. Since particle data are not taxonomically annotated, they cannot be submitted to EMODnet; direct submission to the EU DTO is explored.

D3.4 Updates – The redesign of EcoPart is ongoing (currently financed by another project). HUWO and UVP particle data will be imported into EcoPart and exported as standardised NetCDF files with some quality control checks, for direct import in the EDITO data lake. Currently, all UVP projects from the old EcoPart are being moved into the updated EcoPart; the metadata for 600 projects (UVP5 and UVP6) have been created, but the data have not yet been imported. In parallel, the format of the NetCDF export file to convert the UVP folder format to NetCDF is being finalised. A version is currently under review by the Argo team to ensure that all modifications are compatible with Argo standards.

The SilCam data is already exported as a NetCDF via PyOPIA for direct uptake by the data lake, but the current NetCDF format is being updated for CF and units compliance for improved interoperability.

3.2.1 Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea

The Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO) particle dataset contains particle size distributions from the same continuous imagery monitoring in Helgoland described in section 3.1.3, from 2020 to the present. Particle images will be sent to the EcoPart repository for further processing and direct inclusion in the DTO (pipeline currently under development). This dataset contains ~100M particle images, from 0.04 mm to several mm.

3.2.2 SilCam Particle data from SINTEF Ocean / NTNU OceanLab Marine Observatory (OLMO)

The SilCam particle dataset contains size characterization and concentrations of particles from the same SilCam deployments described in section 3.1.4 SilCam taxonomic data from SINTEF Ocean / NTNU OceanLab Marine Observatory (OLMO). The resulting particle size distributions will be directly included in the DTO either following the PyOPIA pipeline and producing agreed file format or like the process described in 3.2.1.

3.2.3 UVP Particle data

The Underwater Vision Profiler 5 (UVP5) and Underwater Vision Profiler 6 (UVP6) are deployed worldwide, on CTDs, moorings, gliders and Argo floats. Almost all data is centralised in the EcoPart (particle size) and EcoTaxa (images) applications; this represents >40k profiles. Here the focus is on the particle size only, since the images are not sorted to a common taxonomic level across such a large dataset. All projects with open licences in EcoPart will have their data available in the DTO. The UVP5 dataset will contain ~ 14 000 profiles from UVP5s deployed worldwide from 2008 to the present, while the UVP6 dataset will contain ~ 27 000 profiles from UVP6s deployed worldwide from 2018 to the present. The data provided will be particle concentrations and biovolumes within size bins ranging from 128 µm to several mm. These datasets will also undergo preliminary quality control. In addition, a dataset of ~ 2500 profiles from UVP6s deployed on 36 Argo floats will also be made available in the DTO following the EcoPart-DTO pipeline. This dataset will have additional delayed-mode quality control, following the Argo protocols.

4. Data products from “Biologging” (Task 3.3)

Biologging data are data of animal positions/presences obtained by animal-borne electronic devices. For this project, we consider biologging data from animals tagged in Europe, with mainly marine positions. These data are typically stored in Movebank and the European Tracking Network (ETN) database, both hosted in Europe, and can be divided into three types: GPS tracking, archival tracking, and acoustic telemetry.

GPS tracking involves electronic devices (such as GPS and SPOT tags) that record GPS positions. It is a technique that can be used for (marine) taxa with a large enough body size to carry a tag, and that live above or near the water surface (i.e. that breach the surface regularly) so that a connection can be established with GPS satellites. Relevant taxa are large birds, marine mammals (cetaceans), few large fish (i.e. sharks) and marine reptiles (turtles). This type of data is mainly managed in Movebank.

Acoustic telemetry uses a network of receivers that detect animal-borne acoustic transmitters when they pass in close vicinity of a receiver, a technique mainly used for fishes and crustaceans. The transmitters emit an acoustic signal (on a fixed frequency) with a unique ID on a predefined time interval and as the tagged animal moves through a network of receivers, it generates a trajectory. Detection range and therefore position resolution is 200 m on average, albeit being highly dependent on prevailing environmental conditions and tag configuration. Some acoustic tags also emit onboard sensor values such as temperature and pressure. This type of data is managed in the ETN database.

Archival tracking uses electronic tags which store environmental data like water temperature, pressure (i.e. depth), acceleration, oxygen and light. The data are either downloaded from a detached and retrieved device (data storage tags) or directly sent through the ARGOS satellite system (e.g. pop-off satellite archival tags or *PSATs*). The trajectory of the animal can then be reconstructed through geolocation modelling and hence requires processing of the raw data. This type of data can be managed in the ETN database.

For each biologging data type we are establishing (in case not already established) a data flow to GBIF and OBIS which in their turn flow into the EU DTO via EMODnet Biology (Figure 8). The data flow for GPS tracking data from Movebank has been established for 14 datasets: annual data deposits from Movebank flow to Zenodo and subsequently to an IPT DwC-A via the *movepub* R package from where the data runs to GBIF and OBIS; from GBIF and OBIS, data will be ingested

by EMODnet Biology. The dataflow for acoustic telemetry from the ETN database has been established for 8 datasets: from the ETN database datasets are converted to DwC-A via the *etn* R package and via the IPT published in GBIF and OBIS. An overview of the published datasets can be found in the Appendix table. The same workflow will be used for the archival tracking data in the ETN database. However, that data type is currently at the ingestion phase level on the ETN database. Consequently, we are currently developing standardised data outputs for various forms of archival data inputs (which are dependent on archival tag manufacturers and even software versions within a manufacturer).

Two updates are planned in the near future: a) more acoustic tracking datasets will be published and b) the `write_dwc()` function from the *etn* R package will be extended to extract measurement data (e.g. fish sizes, weights and life stages) which in their turn can flow as data products to other relevant data repositories. We are also exploring how raw tracking data from the ETN database can flow into the EU DTO, hence not only the hourly resolutions of DwC format will be used for analysis, but also the high temporal resolution data. This will obviously benefit animal movement research by linking this raw data to environmental parameters to identify how and why animals move.

Figure 8 – Schematic diagram showing the biologging data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow.

D3.4 Updates – For data to flow from the ETN database and Movebank into the EDITO data lake three data pipelines are required:

1. Movebank:

Data in Movebank are organized in studies. Each study has its own metadata and collaborators. The data are organized as reference data (animals, deployments, tags) and measurement data (locations) following the [Movebank data model](#) using terms from the [Movebank Attribute Dictionary](#). Collectively this captures all relevant information for an animal movement study, such as a GPS tracking study. Access to data is controlled by the data owner of each study, who have the option to make the data publicly available.

GPS tracking studies where INBO has administrator rights are deposited annually as open datasets on Zenodo in the Movebank format. They are also aggregated to general occurrence data ([one record per animal per hour](#)) and published on the INBO IPT, where they are ingested by OBIS and GBIF (and from there to the EDITO). The original (non-aggregated) data could also flow directly into the EDITO data lake using the [Movebank API](#). That would replicate existing services offered by Movebank however, i.e. [MoveApps](#). That platform allows users to access and analyze Movebank data, both public data and their private data.

Thirteen GPS tracking datasets on bird movement have been published in EMODnet and are openly accessible.

2. ETN – acoustic telemetry:

The acoustic telemetry data come in two formats: the raw data and the temporally aggregated data. Notably, only open raw data is converted to the aggregated format. That aggregated data flows to OBIS and GBIF, and subsequently to EMODnet, through an IPT sustained by INBO. Because this IPT only runs on datasets where INBO or VLIZ have administrator rights, within the framework of the project we are evaluating if another, more general IPT can be used.

Although still in progress, the raw acoustic data will flow through a direct connection into the data lake via an API (Figure 8.1). The open data flows to the data lake allowing everyone working in the EDITO environment to have access to it. Data under moratorium flows to the EDITO high-performance computing services and is therefore restricted to access via a login.

Eight acoustic telemetry datasets on fish movement have been published in EMODnet and are openly accessible.

3. ETN – archival telemetry:

Archival telemetry consists of datasets with environmental measures such as water temperature, depth and light. Based on these measures, (daily) animal positions can be modelled but therefore do not reflect an animal's true position. Even more, depending on the modelling framework the positions might differ. Consequently, positions obtained via modelled archival telemetry data will not flow to EMODnet, OBIS, or GBIF, but instead a direct connection to the data lake will be established via an API (Figure 8.1). As with the raw acoustic telemetry data, the open data will flow to the data lake and is available for anyone to use, while data under moratorium will flow to the EDITO high-performance computing services and will be restricted to access via a login.

This data flow pipeline is currently under construction, but data import into the ETN database should become available in April 2025. At the moment there are at least three datasets on fish ready to be imported (one from Belgium, two from Denmark) with another (large) dataset from France (i.e. IFREMER) likely to be ready as well.

In addition, because animal trajectories need to be modelled based on the archival data, we are currently establishing a connection between ETN, EDITO and the Destination Earth digital twin. As such, archival data uploaded in ETN will become available for advanced services such as the Global Fish Tracking System (GFTS) and will for example allow the geolocation modelling of animal movements based on the archival data. The output of these models, i.e., the animal trajectories, will subsequently become available in the data lake.

Figure 8.1 – Dataflow of raw, non-aggregated acoustic telemetry data and archival telemetry data from ETN into the EDITO via a direct connection using an API.

Several data products will be created in the coming years through the [ETN Virtual Research Environment](#) (ETN-VRE). These ETN-VREs have as objective to support the community and increase efficiency, standardisation and empowerment of data analyses. The development of the data products will be a collaborative community effort (using GitHub repositories) and priorities for development are set through regular interactions with the community. For acoustic telemetry focus will be given to the creation of automated reports and interactive dashboards. Within

each category several data products can be generated (examples are given in the Figure 8.2). For archival tracking data, summary statistics will be calculated providing information on minimum, maximum, and average daily depth and temperature information. In addition, a geolocation model, run on Destination Earth, but using tracking data from DTO-BioFlow will be developed.

Since the submission of the D3.3 data product inventory, **15 additional fish datasets have been added to the list** to be published in the future.

Figure 8.2 – Ideas for data products linked to acoustic telemetry data.

5. Data products from “Passive Acoustics” (Task 3.4)

Passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) is generally seen as a cost-effective means to survey soniferous species, such as cetaceans, in the long-term without visual confirmation. Generally speaking, this is true with respect to data collection. However, processing the data collected from PAM devices can be computationally expensive and time-consuming. Furthermore, there are various methods and algorithms, as well as environmental confounding factors, which provide challenges when harmonizing data from different sources. For example, many species emit vocalizations that heavily overlap in their acoustic characteristics, making the automated classification to species level difficult without additional data.

Detection of the harbour porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena*) in northern European waters is more straightforward than other cetacean species due to their relative abundance and very high frequency echolocation signal (130 kHz), making them an ideal species for automated detection. The C-POD, and its successor the F-POD from Chelonia Limited (UK), specialize in the detection of porpoise echolocation, or the most common echolocating odontocete in the study area (Cosentino et al., 2024). These instruments, and their common detection algorithm, are fully automated detectors which are used by many different organizations around the world. The output from these units is standardized by the manufacturer, with only the classification parameters varying between datasets.

Due to the challenges associated with PAM detection and classification harmonization, Task 3.4 has focused on creating a data product using C/F-POD harbour porpoise data, with guidelines on how to standardize data collection. However, the collection of data from partners presents its own challenges, as C/F-POD data needs to be processed in proprietary software provided by the manufacturer. This process can be time-consuming, since it depends on the size of the data,

and on requesting data providers to export their data in a standardized manner, which can be challenging. In sections 5.1 Data Formatting and 5.2 Data Aggregation, the issues with C/F-POD formatting are outlined, and our proposed data aggregation tool as a solution which can ensure a high-quality assured data product to flow to the EU DTO. This effort is to ensure that data collected by DTO-Bioflow partners all undergoes the same quality control before being uploaded to a common database, like ETN. Then, the passive acoustic data on harbour porpoise can be aggregated into EMODnet Biology, and then ultimately flow into the DTO Data Lake, as outlined in the Blueprint. The proposed data flow for the passive acoustics data is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 – Schematic diagram showing the passive acoustics data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow.

5.1 Data Formatting

From the website of the [manufacturer](#), any user can download the CPOD.exe or FPOD.exe software, which can be used to extract data from C-POD or F-POD, respectively. This data extraction is completed in two steps: C/FP1 and C/FP3 files. The C/FP1 files are the extraction of all detected data within the deployment, including acoustic characteristics such as the inter-click-interval rate, while the C/FP3 files are the classification of those detections. Presently, as C/FP1 and C/FP3 are proprietary files, they can only be read by the proprietary software.

There are two types of classifiers built into the C/FPOD.exe programs: KERN0 and HEL1. The KERN0 classifier is considered the standard and is employed by most users. The HEL1 classifier was specifically developed for the Baltic Sea region to help manage the critically endangered harbour porpoise population where false negatives can have a great impact on the population management. Further filters can also be applied to the classified data, to help improve data quality in different noise backgrounds (Clausen et al., 2018).

The classifiers and filters applied to the data are not saved within the C/FP3 files in a manner that is visible to the end user, but rather need to be documented independently. Data can only be extracted from C/FPOD.exe into text files in sections, with multiple data settings and formatting options selected by the user. Therefore, not all text files exported from C/FPOD.exe should be considered comparable to one another. Guidelines could be set to request the export of C/F-POD data in a specific way from data providers, however this would highly reduce the likelihood that partners would deliver data to the DTO. Exporting data from C/FPOD.exe is a time-consuming task that the current project would not be able to provide support for.

5.2 Data Aggregation

While C/FP1 and C/FP3 files are proprietary formats that are designed to be read within C/FPOD.exe, tools are starting to emerge that can also read these files. Within the efforts of DTO-BioFlow to integrate cetacean passive acoustic data, we will create a data aggregator that will allow data providers to upload their data directly to an established database, such as the ETN, which already has a link to EMODnet Biology via annual data exports. By making this process simplified for data providers, we can improve the likelihood of participation.

The data aggregator tool would read in C/FP1 & C/FP3 files and associated standardized metadata, and extract the information needed by EMODnet Biology for the data flow to the EU DTO. Presently, the number of detection positive minutes per hour (DPM per hour) are being published in EMODnet Biology once per year. Ideally, raw detection positive minutes would be uploaded, as well as feeding/buzz positive minutes, to indicate porpoise behaviour at a recording location. However, the C/FP1 and C/FP3 contain more information about the detections and their classifications, but there is not a standardized methodology to synthesize these data. Therefore, the C/FP1 and C/FP3 files could then be saved through ETN for future use, if data providers consent.

5.3 Data Sources

- The structure of the ETN database is currently the standard Task 3.4 is working towards, with some adjustments to how metadata is collected and stored. Presently, only porpoise detection data from Belgium and the Netherlands exists within the database, and that data is collected by uploading text files exported from C/FPOD.exe. The ETN has the data flow pipeline to EMODnet Biology, data harmonization, and metadata standardization.
- The HELCOM Biodiversity Database on Harbour Porpoise Acoustic Monitoring Data is presently the largest collection of C-POD data, ranging the entire Baltic Area between 2014-2023. Data collection is possibly still ongoing and will be discussed within HELCOM in late 2024. However, this data is not fully harmonized and is not formatted to be pipelined to EMODnet Biology. This data is also reported as the number of detection positive minutes per hour, and therefore needs to be harmonized before it can be accepted as a data product.
- The National marine environmental monitoring of Harbour porpoise in Sweden dataset contains monitoring efforts around Sweden between 2015-2023, with data being available as porpoise positive minutes.
- A scoping report of existing data sources surrounding the UK, Ireland, and other countries around the North Sea, except Norway, was prepared for the Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (DEFRA) by St. Andrews University (Verfuss et al., 2023). This report identified data providers, including institutions already contributing to ETN, but not existing publicly available datasets. These data providers would be ideal to receive the data aggregator tool.

D3.4 Updates – Harmonisation work of the PAM data is currently ongoing for ETN and the HELCOM Biodiversity database.

Work to adhere to DwC standards requires significant manual processing. A data aggregation tool is currently being developed. In this tool users will provide two inputs: deployment metadata and CP1/3 or FP1/3 files. Deployment metadata, such as start and end time, location, and other information will be supplied by the user to ensure data storage complies with accepted international standards. CP1/3 and FP1/3 files (hereafter, POD files) are generated when the user offloads raw data from a CPOD or FPOD using the CPOD or FPOD.exe, a piece of proprietary software which processes click detections into trains with species identifications. Data can then be extracted from the POD files in a uniform manner, allowing for easier comparison between deployments, projects, and contributors. The tool will take the inputs, extract the information that complies with ETN, and format the data to be added to the ETN database. The data will also go through quality check to ensure that all data feeding into the data lake is harmonised. The data aggregation tool would allow us to include historical “sleeping” data.

Work is being implemented towards automation as additional data is planned to go through ETN with the help of the data aggregation tool. Once complete, the data aggregation tool will export data in DwC standards to be uploaded to ETN and/or EMODnet, or to be directly uploaded to the data lake for long-term storage.

An update of the LifeWatch cetacean passive acoustic sensor network dataset has been published in EMODnet Biology.

The SHARK database in Sweden has independently been linked to EMODnet outside the context of the DTO-BioFlow project.

Work is being carried out to harmonise the HELCOM database, with the objective to ingest the data into the EDITO data lake through a direct connection with ETN, or via EMODnet Biology at a later stage.

5.4 Data Standardization

Metadata is almost as important as the data itself, and what metadata is collected across the different existing datasets varies. Task 3.4 aims to create metadata standardization documentation, which can be distributed to all data providers. Ideally, data from ETN and EMODnet Biology should be compatible with other international data collection efforts, such as [Tethys](#), a freely available open-source temporal-spatial database for metadata related to global acoustic recordings.

D3.4 Updates – Conversations have been initiated with international data holders and data standards boards, both within the EU and within the countries in North America. The DwC standards for PAM detections and classification is presently being defined outside of the DTO, and we have entered the conversation as we will likely be the first to adhere to said standards on such a large scale. The metadata standardisation within the DTO will be compliant with evolving DwC and ANSI standards, which will allow the future incorporation of global data into the EDITO data lake.

6. Data products from “Other Networks” (Task 3.5)

The current section describes an improved and sustainable data flow for a number of additional biodiversity data types and sources necessary for the development of the WP4 DUCs.

D3.4 Updates – An update of the European Seabirds At Sea (ESAS) dataset has been published in EMODnet Biology in April 2025.

6.1 Citizen science data (Task 3.5.1)

According to the White Paper on Citizen Science published in 2015 by the European Commission (Serrano Sanz et al., 2014), Citizen Science refers to the general public engagement in scientific research activities when citizens actively contribute to science either with their intellectual effort or surrounding knowledge or with their tools and resources. In the last years the number of citizens participating in scientific research activities has increased considerably, as well as the number of contributions and datasets.

In subtask 3.5.1, we will explore how we can identify interesting citizen science data sets in OBIS and prioritise them for inclusion into the EU DTO. We are specifically interested into the flow of iNaturalist and eBird data. Marine subsets from these data will be created and ingested into OBIS. In addition, invasive species might be also tagged specifically in the iNaturalist data since this information can be additional provisionally data contributing to the DUC 4.1 on NIS.

For iNaturalist marine data in the UK, there is a high quality and validated data flow coordinated by the NBN Trust, so this could be the basis of improving taxa identification and data flow of iNaturalist and eBird data to GBIF and OBIS.

In addition to the previous data products, a test case will be carried out using low-cost recorders (such as the HydroMoth with Underwater Case) by the citizen science community participating in cetaceans' research in the North-western Mediterranean Sea.

The test case will serve to identify if broadband recorders can identify, with reasonable certainty, positive detections from the different species inhabiting the area, such as Mysticetes (or else Baleen whales) which generally produce low-frequency sounds, and Odontocetes (or else Toothed whales) with more characteristic high-frequency sounds. The test will also serve to check if the implemented detection algorithms provide high quality data (e.g., PAMGuard) and if the employed method is citable and replicable.

D3.4 Updates – The mechanisms for maximising the utility and availability of Citizen Science data for use within digital twins are currently being explored, however, it should be noted that concerns exist around data quality and the persistence of provenance.

Currently, iNaturalist Research Grade data are published to GBIF, however they are not aligned to WoRMS and as such cannot extract a marine-specific component for including within the OBIS infrastructure. Equally eBird data will need to be aligned with WoRMS to provide a marine specific subset for inclusion. Liaison meetings and asynchronous discussions have taken place to explore the ability to tag and extract key taxa of concern, associated with invasiveness. Regional data from an iNaturalistUK project are now routinely screened for a subset of invasive species which is available for download and additionally passed to UK Government agencies for early detection of invasive species. All scripts associated with transformation of iNaturalist data into OBIS-ENV are still ongoing and will be published on organisational GitHub repositories to ensure reproducibility.

6.2 MSFD, Birds and Habitats Directives (Task 3.5.2)

EU Member States are required to inform the European Commission about the implementation of various Directives. Reporting must be done in six-year cycles and is facilitated through a newly developed tool called Reportnet 3. Data can be accessed through interactive dashboards and is available for download in CSV or XLS formats. However, the data is aggregated and not directly accessible.

Some of the outputs of the reporting process could be of use for the EU DTO:

- For the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), layers representing the overall Good Environmental Status (GES) can be extracted;
- For the Birds and Habitats Directives, the Natura 2000 dataset is openly available for use.

In addition, inclusion of other data sources, such as the OSPAR Data & Information Management System and/or the HELCOM databases will be explored.

6.2.1 Data from official reports as part of MSFD, connections with the WISE Marine - Water Information System

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) has several reporting obligations through which the EU Member States have to inform the European Commission on the implementation of different Articles of the Directive.

The processed data, i.e. the calculated Good Environmental Status (GES) indicators, are submitted by Countries via the [Central Data Repository](#) of the Eionet portal or via [Reportnet 3](#), the new e-reporting platform for reporting environmental and climate data to the European Environment Agency (EEA). The data are then quality controlled and imported into a central database hosted by the EEA and later reused for analysis and assessment purposes.

The data are reported per spatial units as indicated by each member country. The spatial units, i.e. Marine Reporting Units (MRUs), are compiled in a different dataset and are linked to the reported data programmatically. The spatial units are available for download through the central data repository, but the reported data are only available to download through the WISE Marine data explorer in a tabular form (Excel). The absence of an API or some other query tool makes the acquisition of the data difficult.

The overall status of each feature per MRU, according to the MSFD GES, can be extracted as a data product and be combined with the Spatial information into a layer for subsequent visualization through the EDITO-infra platform.

6.2.2 Data from official reports as part of the Birds and Habitats Directive, connections with the WISE Marine - Water Information System

The results of the assessment of the data reported under these two directives are published, together with the reporting on bird species under the Birds Directive in a '[State of Nature in the European Union](#)' report. The last report, published in 2020, presents the results of the 3rd reporting cycle for the period 2013–2018. The two directives designate the Natura 2000 areas of protection.

Natura 2000 is an ecological network of protected areas, set up to ensure the survival of Europe's most valuable species and habitats. Natura 2000 is based on the 1979 Birds Directive and the 1992 Habitats Directive. Natura 2000 is the key instrument to protect biodiversity in the European Union. The European database of Natura 2000 sites consists of a compilation of the data submitted by the Member States of the European Union and is generally updated once a year. The Natura 2000 dataset is openly available [here](#); details are provided in the Appendix Table.

D3.4 Updates – Due to data sensitivity, the spatial information of [MRUs](#) is restricted for internal use only and is not publicly available. As a result, visualization or use of MRU-level spatial data within the EU DTO is not an option. Instead, publicly available spatial information is accessible at the regional/subregional level, as defined by MSFD ([link](#)).

The 2024 MSFD reporting cycle is still ongoing, with only about a third of Member States having completed their submissions. To compile a comprehensive dataset, it is recommended to incorporate data from the 2018 reporting cycle.

Status layers reflecting overall assessment conclusions—specifically, whether Good Environmental Status (GES) has been achieved for each GES descriptor and feature in each region/subregion are being investigated. This approach would align with the visualisation presented in the Wise Marine portal [dashboard](#).

6.3 Industrial data (Task 3.5.3)

Within subtask 3.5.3, there will be no data products created (i.e., Data products of Level 4 and Level 5 of the EMODnet processing level scale), but rather there will be biodiversity datasets attained. This will be done via a set of actions that have been set-up in order to increase the number of industrial biodiversity data via different routes that were identified. At the time of writing, we are still in the process of contacting the relevant actors and as such no data sets can be listed. The following routes are considered:

- Using the EMODnet Ingestion network to promote extra uptake of Biodiversity data;
- Analysing the biodiversity data within the UK Crown Estate collection and then get it to EMODnet Ingestion via MEDIN;
- Facilitating the flow of project data around wind parks in the Netherlands to EMODnet Ingestion;
- Investigating which data can be released via the Ocean Decade Corporate Data Group and IODE industry data group and release via EMODnet Ingestion;
- Investigating and reporting on the additional biodiversity data coming in via SEANOE.

The additional biodiversity datasets that will be obtained via these routes will be reported. Important to mention that depending on the used metadata and data standards, not all datasets will reach EMODnet Biology as additional treatment of the data might be needed. Datasets will be prioritised before being quality checked and transformed by the DTO-BioFlow partners.

D3.4 Updates – The role of clearing house/mediator was suggested for HUB Ocean during the “Ocean Data Action Day” (<https://www.huboclean.earth/ocean-data-action-day>), to get industry data elaborated for further uptake in SeaDataNet and EurOBIS from which it would flow to EMODnet and related services. HUB Ocean is a member of the Ocean Decade Corporate Data Group (CDG) and is aiming at data management interaction with industry on a global scale. Discussions between EMODnet/EurOBIS and HUB Ocean took place to try to make more industry biodiversity data available in the right formats via HUB Ocean. Establishment of this collaboration will be explored in the coming months to try set up a dataflow through OBIS or EurOBIS.

MARIS is in contact with Dutch partners to facilitate the flow of project data around wind parks in the Netherlands to EMODnet Ingestion (Wind op zee ecologisch programma - [Wozep](#)).

An analysis of the biodiversity data within the UK Crown Estate collection to get it to EMODnet Ingestion via MEDIN is ongoing. Investigation and reporting on the additional biodiversity data coming in via SEANOE is ongoing.

Company Black Sea Oil and Gas SA has been approached to gain access to marine environmental data related to their operations and establish a collaboration. Black Sea Oil and Gas SA is a Romanian-based independent oil and gas company committed to minimizing environmental impacts through its operations. The company's policy emphasizes continuous improvement in environmental performance, aligning with international standards and best practices.

Connections have been made with Oceanic Club NGO (Constanța, Romania), which is involved in marine mammal observations (dolphins) and the impact of the oil and gas company activities on marine biodiversity.

6.4 Literature based data (Task 3.5.4)

The goal of this task is to mobilise biological and ecological trait data from a wide range of literature and integrate it into existing biodiversity data flows, such as EMODnet Biology. This process involves extracting relevant traits from scientific publications, including both published and unpublished information, and aligning them with existing integrators, such as GBIF and OBIS, and using the WoRMS standardised vocabulary. A key challenge lies in using an

existing method (like text mining, natural language processing, machine learning) that incorporates vast literature resources. There is no single source or method for this. So, leveraging existing tasks is tricky and some of these are still in the research stage (not service level/operational). Initial integration with PREGO (<https://prego.hcmr.gr/>), Plazi (TreatmentBank) and output from the BiCIKL project needs to be further explored and aligned.

Also, structuring the output is a challenge (not all the data can go into WoRMS or be expressed in DwC). The ultimate aim is to create a standardised, interoperable format that facilitates the integration of trait data across multiple platforms, supporting data-driven decision-making in marine ecosystem management.

D3.4 Updates – Current efforts are ongoing to provide biological and environmental trait data sources relevant to the DUC5, which focuses on ecosystem-based spatial planning and Marine Protected Area (MPA) management. This summary synthesizes findings from key repositories such as WoRMS, BIOTIC, and EMODnet, highlighting data availability, challenges, and opportunities for improving interoperability and integration into digital infrastructures like EMODnet and the DTO. While this summary is based on DUC5, the insights and challenges identified have broader implications for other use cases requiring trait data integration.

Data Sources and Current Status:

1. WoRMS Traits Database

- The WoRMS traits framework originated from [earlier phases](#) of the EMODnet Biology project, incorporating information from BIOTIC.
- The current trait attributes in WoRMS are documented at [WoRMS Traits](#) and their definitions can be accessed at [Trait Definitions](#). There is a [R-Shiny app](#) to access this data.
- The database aims for completeness, but gaps exist, particularly in aligning trait data across different sources and ensuring global coverage.
- WoRMS remains open to integrating additional trait information and improving interoperability.

2. BIOTIC (Biological Traits Information Catalogue)

- [BIOTIC](#) is a specialised database designed to support benthic community ecology research by providing biological trait data for benthic species. It enables scientists to analyse benthic communities not only from a taxonomic perspective but also from a functional traits-based approach.
- Provides downloads, but its structure is not fully aligned with WoRMS outputs and DwC standards.
- Some BIOTIC traits were incorporated into WoRMS, but differences in taxonomic coverage and data models persist. See a comparison of one record here: <https://github.com/iobis/dto-bioflow-3.5/issues/32>

3. EMODnet Biology & Trait Data in GitHub

- There are various GitHub repositories and R packages that provide access to Trait data. For example this [GitHub](#) link (from EMODnet) has a CSV file that was last updated 4 years ago. There is also a R package (<https://emodnet.github.io/Btrait/>) that facilitates working with species density data, combined with species traits. Based on the last communication (March 2025), the DUC5 team was not aware of these R packages.

Key challenges identified:

1. Lack of Standardisation in Data Exchange

- Differences between WoRMS and BIOTIC outputs.
- Data formats (e.g., spreadsheets, CSVs) do not align with emerging standards for automated integration (JSON, JSON-LD).

2. Gaps in Trait Data Completeness

- Ensuring global applicability of trait data requires input from diverse editorial teams and stakeholders.

3. Need for DwC Alignment

- Harmonisation of trait data with Darwin Core terms would improve standardisation and facilitate use in global biodiversity infrastructures (e.g., GBIF, OBIS). Also investigating other standards such as <https://ecoportal.lifewatch.eu/ontologies/CMECS> (the Coastal and Marine Ecological Classification Standard) could be useful.

4. Challenges in Literature-Based Trait Extraction

- Automated literature extraction tools for biodiversity data are still evolving. While platforms like Plazi have made progress in extracting taxonomic treatment data, comprehensive trait data extraction remains challenging. Recent machine learning approaches, such as the [study](#) ("From literature to biodiversity data: mining arthropod organismal and ecological traits with machine learning") and tools like [Biodiversity PMC](#) demonstrate promising experimental techniques. However, these methods are not yet sufficiently mature for large-scale, production-level data product deployment across diverse marine taxa.

While progress has been made in documenting trait data gaps and fostering collaboration between key stakeholders (EMODnet, VLIZ, WoRMS, BIOTIC, Plazi, OBIS), challenges remain in making trait data fully data product ready. The next phase of work should prioritise standardisation, repository interoperability, and automation to ensure trait data can be seamlessly integrated into EMODnet and the EU DTO.

Recent research ([Susini et al., 2025](#)) underscores these challenges, noting that many trait-based methods originated in terrestrial plant ecology, leading to inconsistencies when applied to marine benthic ecosystems. The study highlights the need for greater harmonisation in trait definitions, classification frameworks, and methodologies, reinforcing the importance of a unified approach to trait standardisation in marine ecosystem management. The authors also suggest a "translation table" intended for use by trait ecologists when reviewing existing literature that adheres to different trait classifications. While the paper does not mention this explicitly, the table could serve as a foundation for automation, enabling the creation of automated mapping (using approaches like [SSSOM](#)) to enhance FAIR principles and machine readability.

These ideas align with ongoing efforts in DTO-Bioflow to document gaps, improve data interoperability, and ensure trait data is structured, machine-readable, and aligned with established standards such as Dwc.

6.5 Global biodiversity data (Task 3.5.5)

The goal of this sub task is to provide access to these large datasets in OBIS and GBIF of which only parts are currently available through EMODnet Biology. GBIF makes an occurrence snapshot available through cloud infrastructure, which is quite large in size (250 GB per file) and it is difficult to identify the marine data from it.

To solve this problem, we have created a workflow to produce a combined OBIS and GBIF marine species distribution dataset on a very fine grid, which is quite lightweight, but still provides the necessary resolution e.g. for distribution modelling (*speciesgrids* Python package). The resulting data product is fully aligned with WoRMS. Building on this product, a second workflow has been created to overlay species occurrence data with distribution polygons from WoRMS as well as thermal envelopes based on known occurrences (*speedy* Python package).

Finally, species and habitat range maps developed by MPA Europe for all European marine species with sufficient data will be made available as a data product to the DTO.

D3.4 Updates – A workflow has been created to combine all OBIS and GBIF marine species occurrence data in a single gridded product (<https://github.com/iobis/speciesgrids>). This product is built on the periodic snapshots provided by both OBIS and GBIF. For GBIF, species occurrences are first aligned with WoRMS taxonomy and filtered on the

WoRMS environment flags (either brackish or marine). Occurrences are made available in multiple resolutions and grid systems. The data product is available from Amazon Web Services (AWS) S3 as GeoParquet. Notebooks showing how the data product can be accessed and used are available on the GitHub repository above. In a next version, support for additional dimensions such as time and depth will be added. Scheduled updates of the product are yet to be set up, but once this is in place automatic syncing into the EU DTO can be implemented.

All the occurrence datasets of UNESCO/OBIS, including the MeasurementOrFact and DNADerivedData extensions, have been made available on AWS as GeoParquet. Further work is needed to explore if this can supplement the EMODnet Biology data and the data product described above in the EU DTO.

The modelled species and habitat range maps based on OBIS and GBIF data have been finalized and published as GeoTIFF to AWS (<https://mpaeu-dist.s3.us-east-1.amazonaws.com/index.html>). The connection with the EU DTO is expected during the first half of 2025.

7. Conclusions

Since the submission of D3.3, the inventory list has been updated with 16 additional datasets, bringing the number of datasets/data products in the updated data product inventory to 247. Upon submission of D3.4, 29 datasets have been published to EMODnet, including 25 new datasets, and four dataset updates from ongoing monitoring programs (links available in the Appendix table).

During the first 20 months of the DTO-BioFlow project efforts were put to ensure that the datasets from all new biodiversity data types considered in the project adhere to the relevant standards. The time and effort required for standardisation are considerable. All data types have moved forward engaging the relevant communities and progressing with the data transformation work needed to bring these datasets into online repositories following the relevant standards and quality control procedures. Where data delivery to EMODnet is not appropriate, the discussions and work to develop direct data flows to the EDITO data lake have started, with data delivery expected to keep high standards and quality control as relevant for the different data types.

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Appendix

Table 1 – Simplified version of the inventory of datasets and data products.

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
1	3.1	Marine v2.0 catalogue	Bacteria, Archaea	NA	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/genome-catalogues/marine-v2-0	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
2	3.1 (ARMS)	ARMS Jeddah sample Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA308164	NA	NA	NA	ENA
3	3.1 (ARMS)	ARMS Jeddah sample Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004404	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/7bb358e4-6067-42f1-a3e3-7471dd854ce0	NA	NA	MGnify
4	3.1 (ARMS)	ARMS-MBON data on long-term monitoring of hard-bottom communities: COI results from 2018-2020	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB72316	NA	https://obis.org/dataset/066f002f-58d5-4687-bdb8-b39cdaef0c2b	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-	OBIS

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
								000000008357	
5	3.1 (ARMS)	ARMS-MBON data on long-term monitoring of hard-bottom communities: 18S results from 2018-2020	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB72316	NA	https://obis.org/dataset/0ada9b0c-14f5-4247-881e-9f6f62b2c165	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000008617	OBIS
6	3.1 (ARMS)	ARMS-MBON data on long-term monitoring of hard-bottom communities: ITS results from 2018-2020	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB72316	NA	https://obis.org/dataset/ddab58b2-0072-41b8-afc5-ac10d937247f	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000008612	OBIS
7	3.1 (ARMS)	Data from water, plankton and ARMS samples	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB60147	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=gu-2022-wallhamn-coi	NA	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal
8	3.1 (ARMS)	Data from water, plankton and ARMS samples	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB60147	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=gu-2022-wallhamn-18s	NA	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
9	3.1 (plankton)	eDNA data collected in Suva, Fiji by the PacMAN project	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	NA	NA	https://obis.org/dataset/bbc947ad-48c0-4235-8398-3c92f0fc994a	NA	OBIS
10	3.1 (plankton)	Amplicon sequencing of Tara Oceans DNA samples corresponding to size fractions for protists.	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB6610	NA	NA	NA	ENA
11	3.1 (plankton)	Amplicon sequencing of Tara Oceans DNA samples corresponding to size fractions for protists.	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002392	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d596fccb-2319-42eb-b13b-986c932780ad	NA	NA	MGnify
12	3.1 (plankton)	EMOSE (2017) Inter-Comparison of Marine Plankton Metagenome Analysis Methods	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB87662	NA	NA	NA	ENA
13	3.1 (plankton)	EMOSE (2017) Inter-Comparison of Marine Plankton Metagenome Analysis Methods	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00001935	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/20b968fdb7e0-4002-9136-1ccfa8e5b9df	NA	NA	MGnify
14	3.1 (plankton)	Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) 2014: AUTHORITY-RAW amplicon and metagenome sequencing study from the June solstice in the year 2014	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB8682	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
15	3.1 (plankton)	Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) 2014: AUTHORITY-RAW amplicon and metagenome sequencing study from the June solstice in the year 2014	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00000462	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/f6da16a0-ad5a-4f47-a347-aa6281de3dd	NA	NA	MGnify
16	3.1 (plankton)	Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) data from North Adriatic Sea	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB34543	NA	NA	NA	ENA
17	3.1 (plankton)	Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) data from North Adriatic Sea	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005123	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
18	3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2018	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB40757	NA	NA	NA	ENA
19	3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2018	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006608	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
20	3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2019	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB40762	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
21	3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2019	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006607	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
22	3.1 (plankton)	18S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2019	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB56005	NA	NA	NA	ENA
23	3.1 (plankton)	18S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2019	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006610	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
24	3.1 (plankton)	18S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2018	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB55999	NA	NA	NA	ENA
25	3.1 (plankton)	18S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2018	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006611	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
26	3.1 (plankton)	Microbial Processes and Biodiversity: OCEAN	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA414763	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
27	3.1 (plankton)	Microbial Processes and Biodiversity: OCEAN	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002773	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/bd8b945c-6eb4-4301-b6f1-2f4c8047d0ff	NA	NA	MGnify
28	3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA gene sequences (V4 region, DNA and RNA) from Vertical Profiles (surface to 4000m depth) sampled during the Malaspina 2010 circumglobal expedition	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB23771	NA	NA	NA	ENA
29	3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA gene sequences (V4 region, DNA and RNA) from Vertical Profiles (surface to 4000m depth) sampled during the Malaspina 2010 circumglobal expedition	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005718	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/c3212620-a567-402a-b6cc-c8dd50c12f55	NA	NA	MGnify
30	3.1 (plankton)	Amplicon sequencing of Tara Oceans RNA samples corresponding to size fractions for protists	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB7315	NA	NA	NA	ENA
31	3.1 (plankton)	Amplicon sequencing of Tara Oceans RNA samples corresponding to size fractions for protists	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00001789	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a6480411-fc6c-41c9-	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
						bc52-6a6380f1d76e			
32	3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 16S rRNA genes from the tropical and sub-tropical global-ocean sampled during the Malaspina-2010 expedition	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB25224	NA	NA	NA	ENA
33	3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 16S rRNA genes from the tropical and sub-tropical global-ocean sampled during the Malaspina-2010 expedition	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005720	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/1cfb312bfd18-4756-b4f8-89955d05063c	NA	NA	MGNify
34	3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA genes from the tropical and sub-tropical global-ocean sampled during the Malaspina-2010 expedition	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB23913	NA	NA	NA	ENA
35	3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA genes from the tropical and sub-tropical global-ocean sampled during the Malaspina-2010 expedition	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005719	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/c21f2e46c039-4e0c-9b06-1329d733d786	NA	NA	MGNify
36	3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA gene sequences (V9 region) from Vertical Profiles (surface to	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB36469	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
		4000m depth) sampled during the Malaspina 2010 circumglobal expedition							
37	3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA gene sequences (V9 region) from Vertical Profiles (surface to 4000m depth) sampled during the Malaspina 2010 circumglobal expedition	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005717	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/5fe5939e-db73-4ee5-8ed1-69359976a06a	NA	NA	MGnify
38	3.1 (plankton)	Global Malaspina 2010 deep ocean expedition - rRNA pyrotags	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA330770	NA	NA	NA	ENA
39	3.1 (plankton)	Global Malaspina 2010 deep ocean expedition - rRNA pyrotags	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002788	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/ada1f63e-4128-4ea1-a9dd-b8dbf68971d9	NA	NA	MGnify
40	3.1 (plankton)	Global Ocean Sampling Expedition	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA13694	NA	NA	NA	ENA
41	3.1 (plankton)	Global Ocean Sampling Expedition	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00000296	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/512b457b-c410-4381-9911-	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
						900956ceb2d d			
42	3.1 (plankton)	Amplicon sequencing of Tara Oceans DNA samples corresponding to size fractions for prokaryotes or protist	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB4357	NA	NA	NA	ENA
43	3.1 (plankton)	Amplicon sequencing of Tara Oceans DNA samples corresponding to size fractions for prokaryotes or protist	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00000492	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/af30815a-73cb-44a2-82a9-43bd0c580c74	NA	NA	MGnify
44	3.1 (plankton)	The Indigo Project: a global citizen science Ocean survey	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA399019	NA	NA	NA	ENA
45	3.1 (plankton)	The Indigo Project: a global citizen science Ocean survey	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004123	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/c7593664-8288-4f6f-9583-f51cd00e63e2	NA	NA	MGnify
46	3.1 (plankton)	SOLA Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA449267	NA	NA	NA	ENA
47	3.1 (plankton)	SOLA Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00000492	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/62db49d6-	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
					dies/MGYS00004525	860a-48cc-a651-b8ba6d94386c			
48	3.1 (plankton)	SOLA sampling point Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA579489	NA	NA	NA	ENA
49	3.1 (plankton)	SOLA sampling point Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006680	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
50	3.1 (plankton)	Marine fish eDNA metabarcoding	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA802546	NA	NA	NA	ENA
51	3.1 (plankton)	Marine fish eDNA metabarcoding	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006681	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
52	3.1 (plankton)	Vertical stratification of environmental DNA in the open ocean captures ecological patterns and behavior of deep-sea fishes	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA759107	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
53	3.1 (plankton)	Vertical stratification of environmental DNA in the open ocean captures ecological patterns and behavior of deep-sea fishes	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006682	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
54	3.1 (plankton)	Dataset on spatiotemporal variation of microbial plankton communities in the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB55296	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=prjeb55296-18s	NA	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal
55	3.1 (plankton)	Dataset on spatiotemporal variation of microbial plankton communities in the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB55296	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=prjeb55296-16s	NA	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal
56	3.1 (plankton)	Dataset on spatiotemporal variation of microbial plankton communities in the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006678	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
57	3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA gene amplicon time-series in Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory (BBMO)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB38773	NA	NA	NA	ENA
58	3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA gene amplicon time-series in Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory (BBMO)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006675	NA	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
59	3.1 (plankton)	Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory (BBMO) time-series 18S rRNA gene pico- and nano-plankton (10 years monthly samples)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB23788	NA	NA	NA	ENA
60	3.1 (plankton)	Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory (BBMO) time-series 18S rRNA gene pico- and nano-plankton (10 years monthly samples)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006676	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
61	3.1 (plankton)	Bacterial diversity of marine planktonic size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA345534	NA	NA	NA	ENA
62	3.1 (plankton)	Bacterial diversity of marine planktonic size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006677	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
63	3.1 (plankton)	Temporal diversity and community structure of the planktonic protist assemblage at the Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) station MareChiara in the Gulf of Naples (Mediterranean Sea) assessed using V4 Illumina sequencing.	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB24595	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
64	3.1 (plankton)	Temporal diversity and community structure of the planktonic protist assemblage at the Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) station MareChiara in the Gulf of Naples(Mediterranean Sea) assessed using V4 Illumina sequencing.	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006683	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
65	3.1 (plankton)	Metabarcoding Eukaryotic plankton time series samples from long-term ecological research site MareChiara (LTER-MC)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB56637	NA	NA	NA	ENA
66	3.1 (plankton)	Metabarcoding Eukaryotic plankton time series samples from long-term ecological research site MareChiara (LTER-MC)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006685	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
67	3.1 (plankton)	Distribution of chytrids infecting diatoms	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA878459	NA	NA	NA	ENA
68	3.1 (plankton)	Distribution of chytrids infecting diatoms	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006684	NA	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
69	3.1 (plankton)	White sea picoplankton Metagenome	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA368621	NA	NA	NA	ENA
70	3.1 (plankton)	White sea picoplankton Metagenome	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00003126	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
71	3.1 (plankton)	Arctic microbiome along Svalbard Cross Shelf transects	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB24517	NA	NA	NA	ENA
72	3.1 (plankton)	Arctic microbiome along Svalbard Cross Shelf transects	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00003725	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/7c6b6f36-ecab-4ac7-b72c-30e8f501d06f	NA	NA	MGnify
73	3.1 (plankton)	Diversity of Pico- to Mesoplankton Along the 2000 km Salinity Gradient of the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB12362	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=sbdi-asv-3	NA	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal
74	3.1 (plankton)	Diversity of Pico- to Mesoplankton Along the 2000 km Salinity Gradient of the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB12362	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=kth-2013-baltic-18s	NA	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
75	3.1 (plankton)	Diversity of Pico- to Mesoplankton Along the 2000 km Salinity Gradient of the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00001509	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
76	3.1 (plankton)	Environmental DNA and zooplankton samples taken at Helgoland Roads in June 2019	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB59767	NA	NA	NA	ENA
77	3.1 (plankton)	Environmental DNA and zooplankton samples taken at Helgoland Roads in June 2019	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006686	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
78	3.1 (plankton)	18S community profiles at the the end of a spring bloom at LTER Helgoland Roads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB38665	NA	NA	NA	ENA
79	3.1 (plankton)	18S community profiles at the the end of a spring bloom at LTER Helgoland Roads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006687	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
80	3.1 (plankton)	Eukaryotic microbial community at the LTER site Helgoland Roads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB37135	NA	NA	NA	ENA
81	3.1 (plankton)	Eukaryotic microbial community at the LTER site Helgoland Roads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006688	NA	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
82	3.1 (plankton)	Marine metagenome ICM_MPI	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA109345	NA	NA	NA	ENA
83	3.1 (plankton)	Marine metagenome ICM_MPI	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006689	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
84	3.1 (plankton)	L4 fungal time series	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA865278	NA	NA	NA	ENA
85	3.1 (plankton)	L4 fungal time series	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006690	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
86	3.1 (plankton)	16s data marine community of L4 station	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB14618	NA	NA	NA	ENA
87	3.1 (plankton)	16s data marine community of L4 station	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00003999	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/f11d5695-fca8-4e5c-8032-a078b1f9bf65	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
88	3.1 (plankton)	Marine DNA/RNA samples from Western English Channel site L4	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEA46599	NA	NA	NA	ENA
89	3.1 (plankton)	Marine DNA/RNA samples from Western English Channel site L4	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004564	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/7c22d468-97e9-413d-ba04-98d6a5aba181	NA	NA	MGNify
90	3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea 16S gene amplicons from Linnaeus Microbial Observatory sampled regularly since 2011	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB42455	NA	NA	NA	ENA
91	3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea 16S gene amplicons from Linnaeus Microbial Observatory sampled regularly since 2011	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002841	NA	NA	NA	MGNify
92	3.1 (plankton)	Transplant and re-transplant microcosms of Baltic Proper and Bothnian Sea bacterioplankton Targeted Locus (Loci)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA260662	NA	NA	NA	ENA
93	3.1 (plankton)	Transplant and re-transplant microcosms of Baltic Proper and Bothnian Sea	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006692	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a1cd73e2-10d4-4ebf-	NA	NA	MGNify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
		bacterioplankton Targeted Locus (Loci)				8cb2-99268ac44377			
94	3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea 16S gene amplicons from Linnaeus Microbial Observatory sampled regularly since 2011	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB52855	NA	NA	NA	ENA
95	3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea 16S gene amplicons from Linnaeus Microbial Observatory sampled regularly since 2011	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006691	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
96	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2016, 2017 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB52782	NA	NA	NA	ENA
97	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2016, 2017 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006693	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
98	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2015, 2016 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB52780	NA	NA	NA	ENA
99	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2015, 2016 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006694	NA	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
100	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2011, 2012, 2013 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB52772	NA	NA	NA	ENA
101	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2011, 2012, 2013 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006695	NA	NA	NA	MGNify
102	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2011, 2012, 2013 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB52627	NA	NA	NA	ENA
103	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2011, 2012, 2013 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006696	NA	NA	NA	MGNify
104	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2014, 2015 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB52496	NA	NA	NA	ENA
105	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2014, 2015 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006697	NA	NA	NA	MGNify
106	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2017 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB52828	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
107	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2017 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006698	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
108	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2018 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB52837	NA	NA	NA	ENA
109	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2018 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002766	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d89c047d-acfc-4ccd-8627-7e44bd330812	NA	NA	MGnify
110	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2011-16 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3) resequencing	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB52854	NA	NA	NA	ENA
111	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2011-16 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3) resequencing	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006699	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
112	3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea high-frequency temporal study 2012 at the Linnaeus Microbial Observatory Targeted Locus (Loci)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA260661	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
113	3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea high-frequency temporal study 2012 at the Linnaeus Microbial Observatory Targeted Locus (Loci)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006701	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
114	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2013 (3 um)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB56745	NA	NA	NA	ENA
115	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2013 (3 um)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006700	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
116	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2012-13 (3 um)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB56744	NA	NA	NA	ENA
117	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2012-13 (3 um)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006703	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
118	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2012 (3-0.2) resequencing	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB52850	NA	NA	NA	ENA
119	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2012 (3-0.2) resequencing	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002774	NA	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
120	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2015, 2016, 2019 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB52851	NA	NA	NA	ENA
121	3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2015, 2016, 2019 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006704	NA	NA	NA	MGNify
122	3.1 (plankton)	marine metagenome Targeted Locus (Loci)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA196396	NA	NA	NA	ENA
123	3.1 (plankton)	marine metagenome Targeted Locus (Loci)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006702	NA	NA	NA	MGNify
124	3.1 (plankton)	18S rDNA amplicon sequencing of NEREA size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB74658	NA	NA	NA	ENA
125	3.1 (plankton)	18S rDNA amplicon sequencing of NEREA size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006707	NA	NA	NA	MGNify
126	3.1 (plankton)	16S rDNA amplicon sequencing of NEREA size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcodin g	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB74641	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
127	3.1 (plankton)	16S rDNA amplicon sequencing of NEREA size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006706	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
128	3.1 (plankton)	Seasonality of rare and abundant bacterial taxa in Radiales E2 Gijon/Xixon time-series station	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB6399	NA	NA	NA	ENA
129	3.1 (plankton)	Seasonality of rare and abundant bacterial taxa in Radiales E2 Gijon/Xixon time-series station	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006705	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
130	3.1 (plankton)	particle-attached and free-living bacteria kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/SRP158987	NA	NA	NA	ENA
131	3.1 (plankton)	particle-attached and free-living bacteria kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004542	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
132	3.1 (plankton)	Particle -attached and free-living archaea from surface waters of kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/SRP279544	NA	NA	NA	ENA
133	3.1 (plankton)	Particle -attached and free-living archaea from surface waters of kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004542	NA	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
					dies/MGYS00006708				
134	3.1 (plankton)	Planktonic bacterial communities in the arctic Canada Basin and Kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERP001390	NA	NA	NA	ENA
135	3.1 (plankton)	Planktonic bacterial communities in the arctic Canada Basin and Kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004077	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
136	3.1 (plankton)	Kongsfjorden_July_2016	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERP114510	NA	NA	NA	ENA
137	3.1 (plankton)	Kongsfjorden_July_2016	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006709	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
138	3.1 (plankton)	Arctic microbiome along Svalbard Cross Shelf transects	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERP106348	NA	NA	NA	ENA
139	3.1 (plankton)	Arctic microbiome along Svalbard Cross Shelf transects	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00003725	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
140	3.1 (plankton)	Contrasting summer microbiome	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
		communities of the Fram Strait			/PRJNA815464				
141	3.1 (plankton)	Contrasting summer microbiome communities of the Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006710	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
142	3.1 (plankton)	Phytoplankton-derived biopolymers and seasonal bacterial diversity in Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB43926	NA	NA	NA	ENA
143	3.1 (plankton)	Phytoplankton-derived biopolymers and seasonal bacterial diversity in Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006711	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
144	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in Fram Strait (2016-2017)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB43890	NA	NA	NA	ENA
145	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in Fram Strait (2016-2017)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006723	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
146	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in Fram Strait (2017-2018)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB43889	NA	NA	NA	ENA
147	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/stu	NA	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
		Communities in Fram Strait (2017-2018)			dies/MGYS00006722				
148	3.1 (plankton)	Regional and vertical patterns in microbial communities across Fram Strait (2015-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB66267	NA	NA	NA	ENA
149	3.1 (plankton)	Regional and vertical patterns in microbial communities across Fram Strait (2015-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006724	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
150	3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic free-living and particle-associated microbial communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB30254	NA	NA	NA	ENA
151	3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic free-living and particle-associated microbial communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006713	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
152	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in Fram Strait (2017-2018)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB43885	NA	NA	NA	ENA
153	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in Fram Strait (2017-2018)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006712	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
154	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
		Communities in Fram Strait (2016-2017)			browser/view/PRJEB43504				
155	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in Fram Strait (2016-2017)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006715	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
156	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the East Greenland Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB54586	NA	NA	NA	ENA
157	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the East Greenland Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006716	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
158	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the East Greenland Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB54562	NA	NA	NA	ENA
159	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the East Greenland Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006714	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
160	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB67813	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
161	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006718	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
162	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB66202	NA	NA	NA	ENA
163	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006717	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
164	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB66212	NA	NA	NA	ENA
165	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006719	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
166	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB66220	NA	NA	NA	ENA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
167	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006720	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
168	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB65742	NA	NA	NA	ENA
169	3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006721	NA	NA	NA	MGnify
170	3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic bacterial communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB26163	NA	NA	NA	ENA
171	3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic bacterial communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005711	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a69a2cf8-97df-43e8-8c42-5f117204fd68	NA	NA	MGnify
172	3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic eukaryotic communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB26288	NA	NA	NA	ENA
173	3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic eukaryotic communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005711	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/733775df-	NA	NA	MGnify

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
					dies/MGYS00005712	e31f-4742-ac29-81d24c464bff			
174	3.1 (plankton)	Biogeography of Arctic picoeukaryotes during summer of 2012	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB11449	NA	NA	NA	ENA
175	3.1 (plankton)	Biogeography of Arctic picoeukaryotes during summer of 2012	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005715	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/0081f2b0-3c35-4592-9258-2a131bde9fd3	NA	NA	MGnify
176	3.1 (plankton)	Microbial community 16S rRNA from Fram Strait water samples PS85 2014	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB33295	NA	NA	NA	ENA
177	3.1 (plankton)	Microbial community 16S rRNA from Fram Strait water samples PS85 2014	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005713	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d707f7a6-c028-45c5-82ff-e1a22f9ddfe6	NA	NA	MGnify
178	3.2 (plankton imaging)	LifeWatch observatory data: phytoplankton observations by FlowCam imaging in the Belgian Part of the North Sea	Bacillariophyceae, Dinophyceae, Ciliophora, Prymnesiophyceae, Dictyochophyceae	55µm Apstein net sample + High-throughput imaging (FlowCam VS4) + manual validation of images	https://www.vliz.be/en/imis?dasid=4688&doiid=949	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/0ba43f1c-9dc7-4d49-ae90-60d47fd290f3	https://www.eurobis.org/toolbox/en/download/occurrence/dataset/4688	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-	EurOBIS, GBIF, EMODnet

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
								000000004688	
179	3.2 (plankton imaging)	LifeWatch observatory data: zooplankton observations by imaging (ZooScan) in the Belgian Part of the North Sea	Amphipoda, Decapoda, Appendicularia, Copepoda, Cirripedia, Cumacea, Noctilucales	200µm WP2 net tow trough water column, ZooScan imaging, classifier for identification followed by manual validation check	https://www.vliz.be/en/imis?dasid=4687&doiid=951	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a443552e-b521-4d0e-875f-0b96fc860cc7	https://www.eurobis.org/toolbox/en/download/occurrence/dataset/4687	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000004687	EurOBIS, GBIF, EMODnet
180	3.2 (plankton imaging)	Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea	Amphipoda, Decapoda, Appendicularia, Copepoda, Cirripedia, Cumacea, Noctilucales, Polychaetes, Malacostraca, Diatoms	Mooring in North Sea with camera and CTD + High-throughput imaging (CPICS) + automated classification + manual validation of images	Pending	NA	NA	NA	NA
181	3.2 (plankton imaging)	Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea	NA (size characterization of particles)	Mooring in North Sea with camera and CTD + High-	Pending	NA	NA	NA	NA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
				throughput imaging (CPICS) + automated classification + manual validation of images					
182	3.2 (plankton imaging)	SINTEF / NTNU OceanLab Marine observatory	NA (size characterization of particles)	Moorred buoy with telecentric camera on demand and CTD + High-throughput imaging (PyOPIA) + automated classification	Pending	NA	NA	NA	NA
183	3.2 (plankton imaging)	SINTEF / NTNU OceanLab Marine observatory	Pending	Moorred buoy with telecentric camera on demand and CTD + High-throughput imaging (PyOPIA) + automated classification + manual	Pending	NA	NA	NA	NA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
				validation of images					
184	3.2 (plankton imaging)	Koster historical biodiversity assessment	17 species (Ciona intestinalis, Alcyonium digitatum, Caryophyllia smithii, Protanthea simplex, Sabella pavonina, Porania pulvillus, Ascidia spp., Munida spp., Mycale lingua, Serpulidae, Acesta excavata, Actiniidae, Polycarpa pomaria, Phakellia ventilabrum, Molgula spp., Lithodes maja, Geodia barretti)	ROV-based filming	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/51d0bd32-e215-45ea-a04d-47a474336125	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/51d0bd32-e215-45ea-a04d-47a474336125	NA	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000008744	GBIF

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
185	3.2 (plankton imaging)	Species records from remote underwater videos	Carcinus maenas, Ctenolabrus rupestris, Gobius niger, Neogobius melanostomus	ROV-based filming	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/653b41c5-f839-4df9-b6f5-cfb896ac2b52	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/653b41c5-f839-4df9-b6f5-cfb896ac2b52	NA	NA	GBIF
186	3.2 (plankton imaging)	IFCB Taxonomy data CNRS LOG-ULCO. Weekly survey in the eastern English channel EPMO MPA	Phytoplankton	In vivo discrete fresh collected samples	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
187	3.2 (plankton imaging)	IFCB Taxonomy data CNRS LOG-ULCO CGFS (fall) and IBTS (winter) regular fisheries cruises and spring/summer dedicated cruises (weekly survey stops) in the English channel and North Sea (broader coverage than the weekly surveys) ~10M	Phytoplankton	In vivo discrete and continuous fresh collected samples	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
188	3.2 (plankton imaging)	Cytosense taxonomy data CNRS-LOG-ULCO on both weekly sampling at EPMO MPA, CGFS and IBTS regular fisheries cruises and spring/summer dedicated cruises in the	Phytoplankton	In vivo discrete and continuous fresh collected samples	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
		English Channel and North Sea							
189	3.2 (plankton imaging)	Global marine particle size distributions obtained from the Underwater Vision Profiler 5 (UVP5)	NA (size characterization of particles)	UVP5s deployed on various vectors (standalone, CTD rosettes, etc.)	NA	NA	NA	NA	EcoPart
190	3.2 (plankton imaging)	Global marine particle size distributions obtained from the Underwater Vision Profiler 6 (UVP6)	NA (size characterization of particles)	UVP6s deployed on various vectors (standalone, CTD rosettes, etc.)	NA	NA	NA	NA	EcoPart
191	3.2 (plankton imaging)	Global marine particle size distributions obtained from Underwater Vision Profiler 6s (UVP6s) deployed on Argo floats	NA (size characterization of particles)	UVP6s deployed on Argo floats	NA	NA	NA	NA	EcoPart
192	3.3 (biologging)	2010_PHD_REUBENS - Acoustic telemetry data for Atlantic cod (<i>Gadus morhua</i>) in the C-Power wind farm in the southern North Sea (Belgium)	<i>Gadus morhua</i> Linnaeus, 1758	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2010_phd_reubens	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/06d9eb55-ab67-45da-a697-18cc42e7cd3c	https://obis.org/dataset/63061840-e725-4c74-bdbc-65f31a8e28c8	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000005846	Ghent University

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
193	3.3 (biologging)	2011_RIVIERPRIK - Acoustic telemetry data for river lamprey (Lampetra fluviatilis) in the upper Scheldt river (Belgium)	Lampetra fluviatilis (Linnaeus, 1758)	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2011_rivierprik	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/365dcf96-b8ba-49dd-91b8-4aaaa0a0a1a7	https://obis.org/dataset/384580a6-e811-427d-a7a0-1319f6d013a8	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwor k/srv/eng/cat alog.search#/ metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000005867	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
194	3.3 (biologging)	2012_LEOPOLDKANAAL - Acoustic telemetry data for European eel (Anguilla anguilla) in a polder area in Flanders (Belgium)	Anguilla anguilla (Linnaeus, 1758)	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2012_leopoldkanaal	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/0eab323a-364d-4a1b-983b-62b8098845b0	https://obis.org/dataset/f3f5f40c-de45-4f03-b8d7-a4600ae33211	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwor k/srv/eng/cat alog.search#/ metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000005873	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
195	3.3 (biologging)	2013_ALBERTKANAAL - Acoustic telemetry data for European eel (Anguilla anguilla) and hatched Salmon (Salmo salar) in the Albert canal (Belgium)	Anguilla anguilla (Linnaeus, 1758); Salmo salar Linnaeus, 1758	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2013_albertkanaal	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/47360f99-2f92-4e48-9898-1e4976d09d71	https://obis.org/dataset/724eb292-104f-4e8f-8f26-ffa45a1a3be5	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwor k/srv/eng/cat alog.search#/ metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000005868	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
196	3.3 (biologging)	2014_DEMER - Acoustic telemetry data for four	Petromyzon marinus	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource	https://www.gbif.org/datas	https://obis.org/dataset/496	https://emodnet.ec.europa.	Research Institute for

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
		fish species in the Demer river (Belgium)	Linnaeus, 1758; Rutilus rutilus (Linnaeus, 1758); Silurus glanis Linnaeus, 1758; Squalius cephalus (Linnaeus, 1758)		?r=2014_demer	et/8be8dcf1-6e83-4172-a7b7-c2032b933d23	1ff53-d090-497f-9ddb-39b6c485bb66	eu/geonetwor k/srv/eng/cat alog.search#/ metadata/6d6 17269-6e65- 696e-666f- 00000000587 1	Nature and Forest (INBO)
197	3.3 (biologging)	2015_DIJLE - Acoustic telemetry data for five fish species in the Dijle river (Belgium)	Anguilla anguilla (Linnaeus, 1758); Cyprinus carpio Linnaeus, 1758; Platichthys flesus (Linnaeus, 1758); Rutilus rutilus (Linnaeus, 1758); Silurus glanis Linnaeus, 1758	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource/?r=2015_dijle	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/0d9718f4-de6d-4115-b2f0-e3ec6aa088ab	https://obis.org/dataset/64e038e6-795c-418e-b617-7c81e4dcb293	<a href="https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwor
k/srv/eng/cat
alog.search#/
metadata/6d6
17269-6e65-
696e-666f-
00000000587
2">https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwor k/srv/eng/cat alog.search#/ metadata/6d6 17269-6e65- 696e-666f- 00000000587 2	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
198	3.3 (biologging)	2015_HOMARUS - Acoustic telemetry data for European lobster	Homarus gammarus	acoustic telemetry	Pending	Pending	Pending	NA	Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
		(Homarus gammarus) in the southern North Sea (Belgium)	(Linnaeus, 1758)						
199	3.3 (biologging)	2015_PHD_VERHELST_C OD - Acoustic telemetry data for Atlantic cod (Gadus morhua) in the Scheldt estuary and southern North Sea (Belgium)	Gadus morhua Linnaeus, 1758	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2015_phd_verhelst_cod	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/aaf715aa-35c0-4bca-a9f1-03f8c11c2c76	https://obis.org/dataset/5b7fb48c-80ce-4126-bf4d-8b68e1862139	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000006581	Ghent University
200	3.3 (biologging)	2015_PHD_VERHELST_EL - Acoustic telemetry data for European eel (Anguilla anguilla) in the Scheldt estuary and southern North Sea (Belgium)	Anguilla anguilla (Linnaeus, 1758)	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2015_phd_verhelst_eel	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/638cc552-4ca9-43c0-8cad-d3f570a4572e	https://obis.org/dataset/05d3a928-d9de-4855-ac9c-137d12d3a3cb	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000005850	Ghent University
201	3.3 (biologging)	ARMENIAN_GULL - Armenian gulls (Larus armenicus, Laridae) breeding in Sevan National Park and Lake Arpi National Park (Armenia)	Larus armenicus	gps tracking	Pending	Pending	Pending	NA	Pending
202	3.3 (biologging)	CURLEW_VLAANDEREN - Eurasian curlews	Numenius arquata	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/7ee	https://obis.org/dataset/7ee	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu	Research Institute for

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
		(Numenius arquata, Scolopacidae) breeding in Flanders (Belgium)	(Linnaeus, 1758)		?r=curlew_vlaanderen	et/88216808-1942-44ed-b059-b576bf79a28e	5747e-f7c5-44ad-9012-925dd60967aa	eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000007932	Nature and Forest (INBO)
203	3.3 (biologging)	DELTATRACK - Herring gulls (Larus argentatus, Laridae) and Lesser black-backed gulls (Larus fuscus, Laridae) breeding at Neeltje Jans (Netherlands)	Larus argentatus; Larus fuscus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=deltatrack	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/39ca385b-6f25-402c-aa92-a76c89ecda0a	https://obis.org/dataset/9ca26a96-ff54-45f3-a423-7f6ab9f540ef	NA	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
204	3.3 (biologging)	HG_JUVENILE - Juvenile herring gulls (Larus argentatus, Laridae) hatched at the southern North Sea coast (Belgium)	Larus argentatus	gps tracking	Pending	Pending	Pending	NA	Pending
205	3.3 (biologging)	HG_OOSTENDE - Herring gulls (Larus argentatus, Laridae) breeding at the southern North Sea coast (Belgium)	Larus argentatus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=hg_oostende	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/6c860eb3-83ba-48c3-9328-a7b3c7a3c7b4	https://obis.org/dataset/00cad65a-aa33-4d98-93a2-15155fa963e3	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000007921	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
206	3.3 (biologging)	LBBG_ADULT - Lesser black-backed gulls (<i>Larus fuscus</i> , Laridae) breeding in Belgium	<i>Larus fuscus</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=lbbg_adult	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/df50c722-070a-4c6a-a260-3a186ce72fe1	https://obis.org/dataset/6639fa5b-1d59-48fd-a53b-59a3e823fa6f	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000008152	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
207	3.3 (biologging)	LBBG_JUVENILE - Juvenile lesser black-backed gulls (<i>Larus fuscus</i> , Laridae) hatched in Zeebrugge (Belgium)	<i>Larus fuscus</i> ; <i>Larus argentatus</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=lbbg_juvenile	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/83de99ee-92bd-4dc2-a038-a4856f13cd29	https://obis.org/dataset/a8c7c2d3-533a-4b8f-aff8-a43b8f280a7b	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000007937	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
208	3.3 (biologging)	LBBG_ZEEBRUGGE - Lesser black-backed gulls (<i>Larus fuscus</i> , Laridae) breeding at the southern North Sea coast (Belgium and the Netherlands)	<i>Larus fuscus</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=lbbg_zeebrugge	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/355b8ff9-7bd9-49c3-92af-f6741b8bd0cb	https://obis.org/dataset/aac5ca81-638a-4335-9aa7-5c2bda67a362	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000007919	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
209	3.3 (biologging)	MEDGULL_ANTWERPEN - Mediterranean gulls (Ichthyaetus melanocephalus, Laridae) breeding near Antwerp (Belgium)	Ichthyaetus melanocephalus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=medgull_antwerpen	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/ebce3c1f-4307-4539-afb2-3876ec9ae737	https://obis.org/dataset/cd6933a8-797e-41f4-94f0-fcd969b6794e	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwor/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000007938	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
210	3.3 (biologging)	O_AMELAND - Eurasian oystercatchers (Haematopus ostralegus, Haematopodidae) breeding on Ameland (the Netherlands)	Haematopus ostralegus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=o_ameland	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a700359e-a4fa-47d2-9bca-0b8500528cea	https://obis.org/dataset/3b1da04e-7b8d-4080-ba17-d29909d6d95b	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwor/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000007940	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
211	3.3 (biologging)	O_ASSEN - Eurasian oystercatchers (Haematopus ostralegus, Haematopodidae) breeding in Assen (the Netherlands)	Haematopus ostralegus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=o_assen	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/226421f2-1d29-4950-901c-aba9d0e8f2bc	https://obis.org/dataset/550b4cc1-c40d-4070-a0cb-26e010eca9d4	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwor/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000007941	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
212	3.3 (biologging)	O_BALGZAND - Eurasian oystercatchers (Haematopus ostralegus, Haematopodidae) wintering on Balgzand (the Netherlands)	Haematopus ostralegus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=o_balgzand	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/833c03c5-fc23-4e77-8689-4e97fcce96f0	https://obis.org/dataset/2c6aa97e-e886-4564-a55a-48e2e506f014	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwor k/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000007942	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
213	3.3 (biologging)	O_SCHIERMONNIKOOG - Eurasian oystercatchers (Haematopus ostralegus, Haematopodidae) breeding on Schiermonnikoog (the Netherlands)	Haematopus ostralegus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=o_schiermonnikoog	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/361adb42-c1ea-46ed-979c-281ef027cf8f	https://obis.org/dataset/01dbc62a-e166-4752-8547-6db4542ec039	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwor k/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000007943	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
214	3.3 (biologging)	O_VLIELAND - Eurasian oystercatchers (Haematopus ostralegus, Haematopodidae) breeding and wintering on Vlieland (the Netherlands)	Haematopus ostralegus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=o_vlieland	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/cd15902d-3ded-41c2-893d-8840e146cbb3	https://obis.org/dataset/c633b0f8-90bb-43f2-8680-65ac26dd8400	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwor k/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-000000007944	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
215	3.3 (biologging)	O_WESTERSCHELDE - Eurasian oystercatchers	Haematopus ostralegus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource	https://www.gbif.org/datas	https://obis.org/dataset/132	https://emodnet.ec.europa.	Research Institute for

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
		(Haematopus ostralegus, Haematopodidae) breeding in East Flanders (Belgium)			?r=o_westersc helde	et/20bbd36e-d1a1-4169-8663-59feaa2641c0	cf6e-097d-4ee4-b737-58a596dcbe27	eu/geonetwor k/srv/eng/cat alog.search#/ metadata/6d6 17269-6e65-696e-666f-00000000791 8	Nature and Forest (INBO)
216	3.3 (biologging)	SPOONBILL_VLAANDERE N - Eurasian spoonbills (Platalea leucorodia, Threskiornithidae) in Flanders (Belgium)	Platalea leucorodia	gps tracking	https://ipt.inb o.be/resource ?r=spoonbill_v laanderen	https://www. gbif.org/datas et/6850e626-46fd-4843-a391-2c06b069a940	https://obis.or g/dataset/6c7 7ad5e-e635-4c2a-b389-e11676f20137)	https://emod net.ec.europa. eu/geonetwor k/srv/eng/cat alog.search#/ metadata/6d6 17269-6e65-696e-666f-00000000815 3	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
217	3.3 (biologging)	2011_Loire - tracking downstream eel migration in the Loire Estuary, France	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
218	3.3 (biologging)	2004_Gudena - tracking downstream eel migration in the River Gudena, Denmark	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
219	3.3 (biologging)	2011_Warnow - tracking downstream eel migration in the River Warnow, Germany	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
220	3.3 (biologging)	2014_Frome - tracking downstream eel	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
		migration in the River Frome, UK							
221	3.3 (biologging)	2014_Nene - tracking downstream eel migration in the River Nene, UK	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
222	3.3 (biologging)	DAK - tracking downstream eel migration in the Suderpolder and Markiezaatsmeer, The Netherlands	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
223	3.3 (biologging)	ESGL - tracking downstream eel migration from the Grand Lieu Lake into the Loire Estuary, France	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
224	3.3 (biologging)	MICHIMIT - tracking downstream migration of Chinese mitten crabs in the Scheldt river basin, Belgium	Eriocheir sinensis	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
225	3.3 (biologging)	Noordzeekanaal - tracking downstream eel migration in the Noordzeekanaal, The Netherlands	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
226	3.3 (biologging)	PTN-Silver eel-Mondego - tracking downstream eel migration in the River Mondego, Portugal	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
227	3.3 (biologging)	SEMP - tracking downstream eel migration in the River Nemunas, Lithuania	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
228	3.3 (biologging)	2019_Grotenete - tracking downstream eel migration in the River Grote Nete, Belgium	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
229	3.3 (biologging)	EMMN - tracking downstream eel migration in the Alta fjord, Norway	Anguilla anguilla	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
230	3.3 (biologging)	PhD_Goossens: Electronic tagging dataset of European seabass in the southern North Sea	Dicentrachus labrax	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
231	3.3 (biologging)	Rijke_Noordzee: Movement behaviour of Atlantic cod in relation to artificial hard substrates (e.g. Offshore wind turbines and artificial reefs) in the Belgian part of the North Sea (BPNS)	Gadus morhua	acoustic telemetry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
232	3.4 (PAM)	European Tracking Network: Cetacean passive acoustic sensor network in the Belgian part of the North Sea	Phocoena phocoena	PAM	https://rshiny.lifewatch.be/cpod-data/	NA	NA	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d6	Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
								17269-6e65-696e-666f-000000005531	
233	3.4 (PAM)	HELCOM Biodiversity Database	Phocoena phocoena	PAM	https://maps.helcom.fi/web-site/biodiversity/	NA	NA	NA	NA
234	3.4 (PAM)	STRAITS_PAM: Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) during the STRAITS project	Phocoena phocoena	PAM	http://rshiny.lifewatch.be/etn-data/	NA	NA	NA	NA
235	3.4 (PAM)	National marine environmental monitoring of Harbour porpoise in Sweden (SHARK)	Phocoena phocoena	PAM	https://www.havochvatten.se/overvakning-och-uppfoljning/miljoovervakning/marin-miljoovervakning/tumlare.html#Hurdataanvands	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/fbe080fce0c3-4b2c-a6d0-2c017503a3d3	NA	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/81c30c65-5991-47d3-8a2f-58b0f2926990	NA
236	3.5 (other)	European Seabirds At Sea (ESAS)	Aves; Cetacea; Pinnipedia	human observations	https://ipt.vliz.be/eurobis/resource.do?r=esas	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/3470d506e667-4e3f-b178-819669684c05	https://obis.org/dataset/86453e9e-24f5-47b1-b442-b6f86a9979b7	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6d617269-6e65-696e-666f-	Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
								000000003117	
237	3.5 (other)	Pilot test involving the use of low-cost passive acoustic recording instruments by the citizen science community	Cetacea	human observations	NA	NA	NA		NA
238	3.5.1 (other)	iNaturalist research-grade observations	All marine WoRMS taxa	human observations	https://www.inaturalist.org/	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/50c9509d-22c7-4a22-a47d-8c48425ef4a7	NA	NA	NA
239	3.5.1 (other)	eBird	Marine and Coastal Birds	human observations	https://ebird.org/home	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/4fa7b334-ce0d-4e88-aae-2e0c138d049e	NA	NA	NA
240	3.5.2 (other)	Output of the data reported under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). GES Status	2023 revision can be found here: https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/326ae5ac-0419-4167-83ca-e3c210534a69/library/b53eb990-32f7-4c39-b9e3-	human observations	Good Environmental Status (GES) assessments of EU marine waters by integration level-MSFD Art.8 (2018) [full dashboard]	NA	NA	NA	NA

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
			37de3d9c8b2f /details		WISE Marine (europa.eu)				
241	3.5.2 (other)	Output of the data reported under the Birds and Habitat Directive (Natura 2000)	Species list can be found in Annex II of the Directive: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A01992L0043-20130701	human observations	Natura 2000 data - the European network of protected sites (europa.eu)	NA	NA	NA	NA
242	3.5.4 (other)	Custom trait table for ecosystem-based spatial planning and MPA (Marine protected area) management	marine invertebrates	Literature	NA	NA	NA	NA	Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML)
243	3.5.4 (other)	Plazi.org	NA	Literature	NA	https://www.gbif.org/publisher/7ce8aef0-9e92-11dc-8738-b8a03c50a862	NA	NA	Plazi
244	3.5.4 (other)	Biological Trait Information Catalogue (BIOTIC)	NA	Literature	https://www.marlin.ac.uk/biotic/	NA	NA	NA	NA
245	3.5.5 (other)	Combined OBIS/GBIF gridded species distribution data product	All marine WoRMS taxa	Processing of OBIS and GBIF occurrence snapshots,	https://github.com/iobis/speciesgrids	NA	NA	NA	OBIS

No.	Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	EMODnet url	Publisher
				WoRMS taxonomy					
246	3.5.5 (other)	Gridded species distribution product, combining occurrences, distribution polygons, and thermal envelope	All marine WoRMS taxa	Processing of OBIS and GBIF occurrence snapshots, WoRMS taxonomy, WoRMS/WRiMS distributions, Bio-ORACLE temperature layers	https://github.com/iobis/spedy	NA	NA	NA	OBIS
247	3.5.5 (other)	Species and habitat range maps for European marine species	All marine WoRMS taxa	Distribution modelling	https://github.com/iobis/mpaeu_sdm (product pending)	NA	NA	NA	OBIS